

UNITE **4** Horizon Europe

TOWARDS COALITION EXCELLENCE REPORT ON UNIVERSITY-SME COLLABORATION IN EUROPE

Horizon Europe Engagement Programme Framework

**Building collaboration
capacity for Horizon Europe**

Executive Summary

The pace of change of *the liquid modernity*¹ is fostering production of ever-changing reconfigurations generating greater complexity, interdependency and glocalization of social problems that request novel ways of understanding and managing our political, economic, social and technological realities. These novel ways seek foremost to take us from linear mechanistic constructs towards dynamic self-organizing social systems that are not only capable to continuously adapt, but moreover, to drive communities and societies in the desired direction accounting for multitude of differences in values alongside the limitation of available resources. This ability to identify new social developments and quickly adapt to them by being creative in how things can be done, is notably present in small and medium enterprises (SMEs), whose role in the socio-economic ecosystem is to (re- or dis-) connect its various elements through engagement with citizens, clients, interest groups, large universities, big corporations and governments. Oftentimes, SMEs jump in when there is a gap in the system to fill the void by offering services, skills, resources, and techniques. Despite this growing economic role of SMEs, the linkages they create with other organizations, particularly academic and research institutions, remains unexplored.

The research we have conducted as part of the Unite 4 Horizon Europe project seeks to investigate this role of SMEs by concentrating on their relationship with higher education institutions (HEI), i.e. their collaborations and ways such partnerships could be further fostered through training. To do so, we start with a simple premise: that all successful university-business cooperations (UBC) are endeavours of individuals possessing competences that are highly relevant to cooperation and collaboration. We can state that this premise is self-evident as any social endeavour, including UBC, is a direct result of its agents – individuals that shape the activity. This premise stems out of any personal or professional experience too: the better people get at something, the more results improve.

Based on this premise we designed our research which is informed by UBC professionals, and case studies of good practices in HEI and SME collaboration and implementation of European-level projects. By gathering data on their past experiences, opinions and interests we first extrapolate lists of the most relevant motivations, facilitators and challenges for collaboration pertaining to HEIs and SMEs. Our research finds that the most relevant motivators in such circumstances are the following:

◆ Continuous learning ◆ Social impact ◆ Excellence ◆ Social capital ◆ Exchange ◆ Funding

The majority of these motivating factors are equally important as they are interrelated, particularly continuous learning, excellence and social impact on one side, and social capital, exchange and funding on the other. Both our survey and qualitative research support this finding. Therefore, designing future training programmes that build on these motivations should foster participants' learning experience

¹ Bauman, Z. (2013). *The Liquid modernity*. Polity Press.

Table 1: Link between research processes

These motivations are strongly supported by following facilitators, of individual, organizational and policy nature:

- ◆ Commitment
- ◆ Communication
- ◆ Trust
- ◆ Leadership
- ◆ Boundary spanners
- ◆ Networking opportunities
- ◆ Training programs on UBC
- ◆ Level of R&D and innovation intensity
- ◆ Organisational, cultural and social proximities
- ◆ Reputation
- ◆ Quality of education and training
- ◆ Field of study

Facilitators are factors that enable UBC between HEIs and SMEs making it easier and more efficient. This means that lack of these factors in the environment will generate various challenges for initiating and maintaining collaborative projects.

Finally, challenges that UBC practitioners from HEIs and SMEs equally face are the following:

- ◆ Mismatch in: 1) Time-orientation 2) Strategic orientation 3) Focus and priorities
- ◆ Wrong incentives related to: 1) Career advancement in academia 2) Quantification 3) Valorisation
- ◆ Lack of: 1) Time 2) Organizational capacities 3) Financial resources 4) Talent
- ◆ Not enabling policy and regulatory environment:

All these factors - motivations, facilitators and challenges are reviewed in-depth in the first chapter of this report. Based on these findings we identified needs for skills and knowledge by asking what UBC professionals need to know to foster effective collaboration between HEIs and SMEs in Europe. This brings us to the definitions (in the box) of competencies and fields of

knowledge. While there is clear overlap in competencies and fields of knowledge since both entail possession of necessary skills and information about something specific, for the purpose of this report competencies are focused on abilities (the practical know-how) on how UBC should be developed and managed, while the fields of knowledge relate to expertise (in-depth understanding) in specific scientific and/or professional areas that are UBC-enabling.

All identified competencies and fields of knowledge are shown in Figure 1 below. This is not an exhaustive list of competencies and fields of knowledge though, rather we selected the key ones, which are crucial ingredients in excellent coalitions. The second and third chapter of this report provide a detailed overview of those competencies and fields of knowledge. They provide insight into what a mastery of a competency entails and why is it necessary for UBC initiatives and projects between HEIs and SMEs to take off ground and be successfully implemented. The list of competencies and fields of knowledge creates a basis for development of UBC training programmes.

Definitions

Competency is the ability to do something successfully or efficiently.

Field knowledge expertise is possession of content knowledge in specific areas or disciplines.

Figure 1: Competencies and Fields of Knowledge for the HEI&SME Collation Excellence

The Project Consortium

Novatex

A SME in Cyprus, working in different fields with their expertise in university engagement, project participation and management. Novatex holds a close collaboration both with universities and industry and co-organised many information events on the use of technological

Institut Mines-Télécom Business School

One of France's major educational and research establishments. IMTBS has a strong connection to a local network of SMEs in both research and education to support SME innovation and providing education for future employees.

University Industry Innovation Network

An international leader on university-industry engagement, entrepreneurial & engaged universities and knowledge transfer. They conduct research, organise events and provide training and consultancy services to their community of 80+ organisational and 500+ individual members.

Crazy Town

One of the most experienced organizations in Finland that specialises in the subject of promoting university-business-cooperation, in particular, from the practitioners' point of view. They have extensive experience in connecting businesses and universities with hands-on trainings, workshops, and matchmaking activities.

Univations

An affiliated institute of M.-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg, responsible for all strategic entrepreneurship and knowledge transfer activities of the University, bridging between the HEI and enterprise sector in the regional innovation ecosystem.

Meath County Council

A local authority in Ireland, with over 15 years of experience with EU projects – many of them initiated and managed by them. The Council operates the Local Enterprise Office whose emphasis is job creation through enterprise, and which maintains direct and constant links with the HEI across the country and more widely across the EU.

Carlos III University of Madrid

An international oriented university committed to innovation. UC3M has over 230 industrial partnerships on knowledge transfer and business interaction. Their mission is to contribute to the improvement of society through teaching of the highest quality and cutting-edge research in line with stringent international guidelines.

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1. Introduction

The main goal of the *Unite for Horizon Europe (UNITE4H)* project is to help build strategic engagement capacity between European academics/researchers and SME representatives to increase the proportion of successful collaborative participation in the Horizon Europe initiatives. To achieve this goal, the project seeks to achieve the following:

1. identify the engagement needs and challenges experienced & collaborative opportunities envisioned by the academics and SME representatives across Europe;
2. develop a Horizon Europe engagement training programme to increase awareness, skills and knowledge capacity among academics and SME representatives; and
3. validate the training programme via pilot testing and workshop sessions.

Although the relationship between universities and SMEs is not expansive in Europe, a shift is evident in the new support schemes and funding programs, especially at the European level. Thanks to the strategic transition from generic to specific issues and challenges, involvement of SMEs in UBC can become more substantial and meaningful. Moreover, partnerships with SMEs can foster innovation, technology catch-up and direct industrial and wider social engagement of academics. The innovative role of SMEs in the new economies can then take its full potential.

Our intention is that this report is useful for all UBC practitioners, especially to HEI and SME representatives. Considering the fact that the extent of UBC is relatively low across European countries, by doing this research and sharing its results, we hope to improve the understanding of UBC. In particular, we want to extend the knowledge base about the current state of UBC, particularly with respect to motivations, challenges, mechanisms supporting collaboration, and the skills and competencies required to engage in such collaborations by focusing on HEIs and SMEs.

Finally, by sharing specific knowledge about potential opportunities for universities and businesses to acquire i) training in UBC competencies and fields of knowledge, and ii) funding through the Horizon Europe program, we hope to broaden and promote coalition building excellence for joint research, education and valorisation in Europe.

The first chapter of this report provides overview of the HEI & SME collaboration in Europe by focusing on the motivations, facilitators, challenges and supporting mechanisms for UBC initiatives and EU funded projects. Based on our extensive data collection, this chapter aims to provide a nuanced overview of

how UBC is driven, what kind of barriers it faces and what supporting mechanisms are in place. It does so by providing insights on actual HEI and SME Collaboration in European and national context in Cyprus, Finland, France, Ireland, Germany, and Spain. It summarizes and highlights the most relevant research findings in light of training needs and possibilities. The second and third chapters entail a review of competencies and fields of knowledge for successful UBC in context of HEIs and SMEs. These present the basis for development of a training for the Horizon Europe Engagement Programme for Framework. In the final chapter of this report an overview of various opportunities is included where learning and access to UBC resources can take place. The Methodology chapter provides overview of the methodology used and research conducted for this report.

2. HEI & SME Collaboration in Europe

University-business cooperation (UBC) is 'any sort of interaction between universities and business for mutual benefit' (Davey, Baaken, & Galan Muros, 2011). These interactions can take place in teaching, research, valorisation, or are part of management activities. In literature these interactions are classified in the following categories: 1. curriculum development and delivery; 2. lifelong learning; 3. student mobility; 4. academic mobility; 5. commercialization of research and development (R&D) results; 6. collaboration in R&D; 7. entrepreneurship; and 8. governance (Seppo & Lilles, 2012; Davey et al., 2011).

For the purpose of our research, we treat motivations as factors that drive UBC, while facilitators are elements that enable it. Challenges are barriers that hinder or reduce UBC, while opportunities and supporting mechanisms do the opposite, they foster and cultivate UBC.

This chapter provides overview of motivations, facilitators and support mechanisms for the UBC and focuses on collaboration between HEIs and SMEs. Both sides share some factors, while in some instances they are different.

2.1. Motivations

Although the term "motivation" is primarily used in personal contexts, for the purpose of this report, we use the term to refer both to individuals and organizations. The reason behind such an approach is that research results illustrate close and complex relationships between individual and organizational motivators. Indeed, one of the most conspicuous research findings is the interrelated nature of organizational/company policies and structures and personal traits and abilities of academic, researchers, SME representatives and university management. Professionals drawn to cross-sectional engagement open their institutions, while the opposite is also true: open and collaborative organizations are appealing to engaged researchers and SME managers. This fact leads us to the first motivation or trait characteristic of engaged HEIs and SMEs: openness for diversity. Namely, successful HEI-SME collaborations and engaged institutions in both types of these organizations showcase aptitude for diversity: interest to get involved with social actors coming from different sectors, disciplines and fields and concern for their experiences, practices, and way of knowing and working. Thus, engaged HEIs and

SMEs are open to working and learning from or with diverse social groups. This engagement is driven by the motivation for **continuous learning, reflection and in-depth understanding** of problems and development of potential solutions. As such, engaged HEIs and SMEs are open to new ideas, novel technologies and other inventions that can improve their mode of operations or their services/products. This openness is crucial for engagement, which does not only entail openness to novelty, but also openness to making mistakes and learning from them. The prospect of being able to use the trial and error method in a safe environment is particularly important for academics, researchers and SME representatives as it allows them to learn and innovate. Indeed, innovation is result of continuous learning process in an environment where diverse people and their ideas interact over time. Therefore, one of the main motivations for engaged academics, researchers and SME managers is learning, whereas their organizations - HEIs and SMEs – structure and formalize it into the process of knowledge production.

From the outset, it is important to emphasize that learning and knowledge production in engaged organizational settings is not only continuous and reflective, but it is predominantly concentrating on real-world problems. This aptitude for applied knowledge is driven by the need for social impact, not only by universities but businesses are motivated to address social challenges too (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000; Galán-Muros & Plewa, 2016). Particularly in the recent period, desire for **social change and meaningful social impact** has been evident and noticed in our research as well. People want to do meaningful work rather than just have jobs. This desire for social change is oftentimes directed towards novel and complex socio-economic, environmental and technological problems arising out of the accelerated globalized development. Especially participation in the European-level projects provides ways to generate greater social impact and address issues transnationally. Such international engagement yields experience which both HEIs and SMEs in all investigated country contexts find quite important as it enables them to communicate with leaders in the field. Thus, such engagements generate **relevance and credibility** to involved professionals and organizations.

This aspiration for relevance and credibility through UBC is evident in both HEIs and SMEs and is closely related to the motivation for **competency and excellence**. Participation in UBC, and particularly EU funded projects, showcases capacities, the knowledge base, potential and social role of involved stakeholders. In turn, it raises their visibility and esteem in the field, which later on bring in new contacts, projects and initiatives. Particularly for HEIs, valorization and commercialization of research as well as collaborative R&D projects, increase research competencies and international standing of the university. These factors are nowadays used as indicators for knowledge/technology transfer and organizational innovation in international assessments of HEIs. For SMEs, collaboration with HEIs presents not only a way to collect profit but also to develop competency in design and implementation of European projects, widen their networks and to increase their market value. The same is true for HEIs too, even for profits, as public funding for universities is decreasing in many countries.

Another motivation that is evident in literature (Metcalf, 2010; Ankrah and Al-Tabbaa, 2015) but also from all conducted interviews is the aspiration to generate new contacts, widen professional networks and in general **raise its social capital**. Both HEIs and SMEs find European and international level projects particularly important in this regard as it opens organizations to novel communities of knowledge and practice, markets and networks. Particularly business are driven by the need to compete in the international market (Davey et al., 2018).

Figure 2: UBC Motivations for HEIs and SMEs based on our qualitative research

All aforementioned factors together are crucial for **professional development and growth**, both in financial and non-monetary aspects. UBC in all aspects, teaching, research, valorisation, or are part of management, supports generation of new ideas, projects, products, services, etc. It creates new opportunities and acts as springboard of future developments. This fact is one of the strongest motivations for SMEs for participation in European funded projects, as it propels them onto regional and international markets and opens up new prospects. They are particularly interested in commercialization of products, creation of spin-offs, start-ups and other by-products resulting from UBC. From companies' perspective, universities can generate outputs which then can result in new business models, or to improvement of products or services. Many companies, especially SMEs, have limited resources for research which universities can provide.

These collaboration outcomes result from **organizational exchange in knowledge, talent/staff, training, technologies and other various resources**. Through UBC, HEIs are able to access information on industry problems (D'Este and Perkmann, 2011), business expertise, industry knowledge, and business sector (R&D) facilities (Tartari and Breschi, 2012). Businesses are also able to access non-monetary resources (Ankrah and Al-Tabbaa, 2015), cutting-edge scientific knowledge in early stage (Kock et al., 2000; Lee, 2000), university facilities (Schartinger et al., 2002), new products and services (Bercovitz and Feldmann, 2006; Bekkers and Bodas Freitas, 2008), and applicable knowledge from universities (Bruneel et al., 2010; Bodas Freitas & Verspagen, 2017). Like universities benefit from industry problem solving, businesses benefit from the problem-solving ability of academia (Van der Sijde, 2012; Lee, 2011), and report an acceleration in their innovation process (Hewitt-Dundas, Gkypali, & Roper, 2019; Dan, 2013; Metcalfe, 2010). Our research finds that HEIs oftentimes cooperate with SMEs which offer services in development of online courses, for which the need has significantly increased in the recent period, and particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Mobility and hiring of students and staff, through internships or exchanges with businesses, HEIs find quite relevant since businesses engagement can both influence the skills alignment and development of students (Ginzburg & Houli, 2013; Muscio & Vallanti, 2014), and profit from upskilling and retention of existing staff (Healy, Perkmann, Goddard & Kempton, 2014). Also, SMEs oftentimes provide professional consultancies for writing project proposals and legal expertise, which some universities do not have in house. On the other side, SMEs find access to technologies and equipment in possession of HEIs enormously useful since they cannot acquire those on their limited budgets. Therefore, exchange in knowledge, talent and technologies helps both sides to **address their resources needs and limitations**.

The aforementioned motivational factors are evident across the European and all national contexts investigated in our research. However, differences in historical, cultural and institutional norms and experiences do generate variations in motivations. For example, when compared with their European counterparts, French HEIs appear to be more focused on generating social impact and increase graduate employability through UBC. Whereas promotion- and reputation-related motivators are the weakest UBC drivers for academics in France. This is understandable since UBC is not included in performance measurement in the French HEI system. Reputation, especially in public universities, is primarily formed on the basis of the number and the quality of publications.

On the other hand, in Ireland, where research and innovation are the cornerstone of its economic development policy, HEIs have an important role in R&D and lots of UBC focuses on these efforts. Major part of Irish innovation is driven by university and research institutes partnering with business. Likewise, HEIs in Germany have an important role in country's R&D efforts. In Germany, every 6th Euro spent on R&D is coming from HEIs (Stifterverband & Heinz Nixdorf Stiftung, 2019). HEIs are seen as important partners for German companies which invest around 1,4 Billion Euros into HEI research per year.

(Stifterverband & Heinz Nixdorf Stiftung, 2019). Main motivational drivers for German HEIs to engage in UBC are:²

- access to third party financial resources and funding;
- opportunity to apply scientific results;
- gaining new relevant knowledge from practical applications;
- opportunity to practically apply scientific knowledge;
- higher visibility of research results and potential gains in reputation;
- benefit from research potentials of new (non-university) partners.³

Interestingly, German companies are no longer looking primarily for collaboration that promise short-term pay-offs. Rather, engagement in joint (basic or strategic) research efforts with a long-term valorisation perspective have become increasingly popular – also because they may bear more potentials for disruptive or radical innovations as short-term oriented endeavors (of applied research).⁴ Motivational factors for German companies to engage in UBC (even without public support) have remained rather persistent over time. They are:

- access to new technologies and the (university) partners' know-how;
- securing the firm's competitiveness;
- time benefits;
- cost reduction;
- risk diversification;
- synergy effects;
- contact with potential employees.⁵

Similarly, Finish businesses are proactive in undertaking UBC and motivated foremost by the following:

- access to a new talent and recruiting students;
- utilization of new technology and knowledge;
- improving organizational R&D capability;
- upskilling existing workforce and talent development.⁶

2

C. Herstatt, C. Raasch, S. Buse (2007): Kooperationen zwischen KMU und Hochschulinstituten Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze; K. Koschatzky and T. Stahlecker (2016: Public-private partnerships in research and innovation: Trends and international perspectives); G. Koglin (2011: Wie neues Wissen in die Wirtschaft kommt).

⁴ K. Koschatzky (2014): Regional Engagement of Universities – Starting Points for Strategic Partnerships with Industry (presentation).

⁵ C. Herstatt, C. Raasch, S. Buse (2007): Kooperationen zwischen KMU und Hochschulinstituten Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze, K. Koschatzky and T. Stahlecker (2016): Public-private-partnerships in research and innovation: Trends and international perspectives.

⁶ Jääskö et al., 2019.

2.2. Facilitators

Facilitators are the factors that can foster engagement. Rast et al. (2015), have identified **commitment, communication, trust, and leadership** as the main factors in the engagement process for both universities and businesses. Commitment is defined as the lasting aspiration to build and maintain UBC, allowing both parties to reach their individual and common aims and objectives (Moorman et al., 1992). Communication is the basis for information exchange and knowledge sharing, especially between the different parties. This in turn enhances trust, which is crucial for building and maintaining collaboration (Bruneel et al., 2010). The role of leadership is to actively support the engagement (Galan Muros et al., 2017; Rast et al., 2015).

According to Rosli (2018), the following three factors need to be present in SMEs for successful engagement. First, there needs to be a **boundary spanner that can create the bridges** both between the SME and HEI, but also within the SME itself (Rosli, 2018; O'Reilly, 2017). Second, there needs to be a committed SME leadership that can allocate the needed resources and that actively encourages open communication. This will broaden the engagement within the SME to include those outside the collaboration project to explore further opportunities. Rosli also places some responsibility with the policymakers and funders to support these SME leaders to develop the relevant skills and capabilities. Another role for policy actors is in contextually constructed criteria for funding. By moving away from national standards, the funding schemes will be easier matched to the regional knowledge potential (Mathisen, 2021). Third, there needs to be a strong relationship between the university and SME, characterised by trust, cognitive proximity, open discussions, and acknowledgment and respect for the different roles and responsibilities (Rosli, 2018).

The development of trust between both parties can be supported through creating **networking opportunities**. In an early stage of the engagement, the trust for SMEs in university is mostly based on the competency of the universities as a whole, rather than a specific department involved and referrals (Darabi, 2020; Giones, 2019). Universities can actively support this by creating formal and informal networking opportunities for SMEs and encourage them to talk to each other about their experiences (Darabi, 2020). It is also important for universities and SMEs to develop a personal relationship, especially using face-to-face interaction (O'Reilly, 2017). There is also a role for universities to support SMEs, namely by promoting, recognising, and valuing partnerships with SMEs (O'Reilly, 2017).

While many **training programs on UBC** are aimed at the academic researchers that drive engagement, it would be beneficial for both parties to participate in training programmes (Giones, 2019). SMEs that are new to engagement with universities can be supported through innovation support programmes to

increasingly build up their absorptive capacity. They should be aware that they might not right away gain all the benefits from engagement. Especially ‘action learning’ and ‘organisational development’ elements in such programmes contribute to the absorptive capacity and engagement capabilities in SMEs (Kurdve, 2020).

Geographical proximity is not necessarily a condition for HEI-SME engagement. It is rather the **organisational, cultural and social proximities that are essential** (O’Reilly, 2017). However, geographical proximity would enable easier interactions within a region, which in turn can increase the trust (Giones, 2019). For example, within France, geography is a leading incentive for collaboration. 94% of businesses collaborate within their region and 92% within country. However, 79% of businesses also report international collaborations, made possible by various EU funded projects (Davey & Meerman, 2017). Certain geographical areas host specific industries that have been able to create international connections. After Paris, Montpellier region has majority of research organizations in France

Figure 3: UBC Facilitators for HEIs and SMEs based on our qualitative research

and encourages creation of innovative start-ups. As such, the geographical proximity acts as a UBC facilitator and generates new business opportunities but mostly for researchers and experts in IT and other related fields. Certain countries have profiled themselves as experts in specific field. For example, Finland fosters arctic skills and knowledge as its strategic niche based on their natural environment.

Ireland on the other hand has embraced investment in innovation as a key driver for the financial recovery of the country after their crisis. Generally, Germany ranks high in UBC when compared to its counterparts in the EU.⁷ This score is closely connected to the worldwide top position of the German economy in terms of R&D and innovation activities (R&D-Intensity of 3,17%⁸ in 2019 makes Germany as one of the most research intense economies in the world). About 59,9% of all companies in Germany reported that they have undertaken innovation activities in 2019.⁹ Clearly, the overall **level of R&D and innovation intensity** in which HEIs and SMEs operate acts as a facilitator as better and higher matches for UBC in terms of competences and interests of involved stakeholders are possible, as well as, there are already existing networks of joint collaborations (e.g. clusters, innovation alliances, etc.).

Thus, past experiences generate learning and trust which further facilitate collaborations. As it has been elaborated at the beginning of this chapter, trust between parties is essential for UBC. However, before SMEs have built up a relationship with a university, their trust is based on the competency of the whole university, rather than a specific department. In this way, **reputation** is closely related to trust and can facilitate collaboration. Reputation itself can be built on past UBC experiences but also in education, since academic research and UBC is directly related to **the quality of education and training** at a university. Greater support to students and inner school system is crucial as well as fostering entrepreneurial and engaged education. In educational systems, where teaching is performed through direct social and/or industrial engagement, UBC naturally occurs and is later transposed into collaborative research and joint innovation.

Finally, the **field of study** may also influence the HEI's ability to engage, as engineering academics engage in formal research activities, including joint and contract research, far more than do social sciences and humanities researchers, who engage more in informal activities with industry partners.

2.3. Challenges

Time is the most precious resource. This is true for UBC and for development and implementation of national and European funded collaboration projects too. Oftentimes, UBC and joint projects are additional activities for majority of involved stakeholders, particularly academics, who conduct research, teaching and have administrative duties at universities beside their UBC work. Also, focus of SME representatives is on generating profits and ensuring their company stays afloat despite the limited resources it possesses. Apart from large HEIs or big companies that have allocated staff and/or large

⁷ T. Davey et al. (2013): The State of University-Business Collaboration in Germany.

⁸ R&D intensity = expenses on R&D as share of gross domestic product.

⁹ ZEW (2021): Innovationen in der deutschen Wirtschaft.

UBC-related departments (Knowledge/Technology Transfer Offices, Innovation Offices, IP teams, Partnership Departments, etc.), other stakeholders rely on their regular staff to manage all UBC tasks. In such circumstances, it is understandable that **time to perform UBC is missing**. Academics at HEIs or SME representatives are not allocated enough time for finding partners, negotiations and other tasks required to build the consortium and apply for funding.

Another time-related challenge is **the difference in timeframes** of HEIs compared to businesses and especially SMEs. Particularly businesses have the expectation that UBC and EU project related outputs are to be managed more quickly and thus more efficiently. SMEs find academic institutions slow and existing in a different time horizon. This slow pace of operations occurs in large teams in complex European projects as well. Managing large consortiums out of a single organization is challenging as it requires lots of time. Especially universities have “rigid” administrative procedures and European and other applications grants require a lot of time to be addressed properly. This **high level of bureaucracy** costs a lot of time, especially SMEs, that negatively impact initiation, creation and implementation of UBC initiatives in general and European funded projects. In fact, for the larger funding programmes, like Horizon 2020, the time scale is one of the biggest barriers. Even with the specific SME Accelerated Application process companies are looking at a nine-month window from application to grant awarding. This timeframe only relates to the period to get the project started. This is incredible amount of time for a very small company. Such timeframe combined with chances of winning such projects are, at best, 20%, it becomes very difficult for SMEs to engage. “Small companies are too busy surviving to think long term”, an interviewee stated. Thus, SMEs need to be very agile in decision-making, strategy, development and commercialization.

In this way, the time mismatch between HEIs and SMEs does not only happen due bureaucratic issues, but due to **the difference in strategic orientation** of these distinctive types of organizations: HEIs (including EU funded projects) are long-term oriented as new lines of research and innovation require lengthier periods of time for realization, whereas SMEs focus on capturing value through short and medium term targets to be competitive and financial solvent. Due to this fact, their priorities are different too. The strong **difference in focus and priorities** between HEIs and businesses is especially evident when expectations and desired outcomes from UBC and EU funded projects are investigated.

Academics prioritize research and publications, while businesspeople favor prototype testing and products and services that can be commercialized. The **career development incentives in the higher education systems do not support social engagement or industrial transfer**, rather they foster publications efforts in academia. Salaries in academia are also not incentivized for the knowledge transfer neither (researchers rarely receive bonuses or commissions for participation in externally funded projects from which HEIs directly benefit). In many circumstances, academic researchers must put aside their scientific work to collaborate with external stakeholders, damaging their professional projection.

Consequently, only small proportion of academics actually engages in UBC and develops research and/or collaborative projects. This is something that was stated by HEIs representatives too. Due to this lack of engagement, business representatives find that majority of academics and **universities neglect the social reality and especially the market needs**. Even when good technologies and solutions are developed through joint projects, **HEIs lack ambition to access the market**, which would increase interest from international investors and generate new opportunities. SMEs find that such neglect of the social and market needs makes **HEIs lag behind in cutting edge research and finding suitable socio-technological solutions**. SMEs find that some research at universities is outdated as there is strategic disconnection in academia and even in national research funding agencies with the constantly changing socio-technological developments and even the European funding strategic focus areas, such as the innovative role of SMEs in the current economy or the Green Deal. The green transition and climate change are examples of complex global problems that require novel forms of research approach and social action. Transdisciplinary and multidisciplinary are becoming increasingly important and learning how to work in such co-creation processes requires university researchers and managers to rethink how departments operate, how to structure research teams and how to work internally and externally. Especially the European funding focuses on cutting edge research and technologies, which require set up of joint teams across organizational borders and continuous insight about newest developments, opportunities and work of others, including what is happening on the ground. A high focus on real-time empirical data is evident. These developments are reshaping how science is done. In particular, the open science and the citizen science methods are taking strong foothold in novel research but also in EU funding requirements.

In general, all our research informants highlight **a mutual ignorance and inexperience in working in/with different sectors**. While HEI representatives do not have clear understanding of the business environment, SMEs showcase disapproval of how academia operates. This ignorance extends to the potential benefits UBC and joint projects can bring them - the competitive and differential advantages for both parties – and potential mechanisms for collaboration. Consequently, **communication is scarce and ineffective** as well, even when collaboration is established. The main reason for this problem is the lack of training in UBC but also the fact that small number of people have actual experience working in academic and business settings. In general, a lack of UBC expert bodies and consultants that can bring these two types of organisations together is emphasized. Fostering UBC expertise sets grounds of development of mutual understanding and language. In many cases industry players and university people speak two different languages so an interpreter is needed. Oftentimes, this involves finding a common denominator of interest: while HEIs are interested in a research result, companies are interested in the potential of that result. Successful and long-term partnerships are built on shared interests.

A particularly important aspect of identifying shared interest are the intellectual property rights and definition of risks and profits to be shared between involved parties in UBC. **Risk and profit sharing in**

technology/knowledge transfer are problematic as clear practices in Europe have not been established in many countries. Negotiations on such issues takes place on case by case basis but generally, throughout interviews it was stressed that academics stipulate requests that business partners do not find financially beneficial. While researchers highlight the value of the idea and solution they developed, business representatives point out the level of risks companies have, especially SMEs, when investing in application of that solution on the market. Successful partnerships and long-term UBC collaboration often resulted from good negotiations on risks and profit sharing, but also with the support of experts in intellectual property rights. Appropriation and distribution of intellectual property rights is a complex issue, requires expertise in national regulations and European funding requirements.

Figure 4: UBC Challenges for HEIs and SMEs based on our qualitative research

Besides finding common interests, **finding suitable partners is challenging**. This is another aspect where UBC expert bodies and consultants are having an important role, which can be further extend. Since UBC entails collaborative activities between distinctive types of organizations from different sectors, identifying and establishing contact with best partners is challenging. In the first instance, finding the right partner requires insight not only in what others are doing but also their approach and needs, so the established partnership is match in values, methods and interests. Only in such cases, HEIs and SMEs find UBC to be useful. Oftentimes, companies are not aware who are the leading research groups in a sector, and researchers/HEIs are now know which companies might interested in their technology or who might need the knowledge they have. Although many knowledge centers and online tools are available today,

due to the information overflow, access to useful UBC related information on opportunities and stakeholders is difficult, especially for startups and SMEs, since they do not have departments that large companies have which would segment and organize the available information. Also, **finding current, not outdated information is challenging**. Various support is available, but finding it, is not a straightforward process for many. Particularly for SMEs it is difficult to create consortia for the European funding applications. Sometimes SMEs are brought into consortiums since there is a funding requirement in a project grant without proper insight in what such participation entails. In such cases, their engagement is not substantive, or issues arise as they were not aware of legal conditions, administrative and reporting requirements and obligations that continue beyond the lifetime of a project.

Organizations, in this instance foremost HEIs, are able to overcome these challenges if they have integrated internal support to address all aspects of UBC and implementation of European funded projects. However, majority of HEIs and SMEs do not have access to such resources, and they **lack organizational capacities, particularly in staff and expertise in UBC and European funded projects**. Then starting UBC and a joint proposal can be quite intimidating. Particularly large projects are challenging for SMEs as they do not have capacities to successfully engage in all aspects of such projects. For example, UBC entails regular meetings and team conferences where decisions are made, but these events directly take staff and time from SMEs from their regular business operations. Although costs for these events are covered, SMEs do not have sources from which they can cover up for lost time and work as their staff base and budgets are limited. On the other hand, decision making in HEIs can be quite complex. Again, large bureaucracies are perceived as a barrier by most research participants. Another organizational barrier that was oftentimes mentioned are **missing cultural and language skills**. As UBC and European projects often incorporate international cooperation, understanding of how things are done in different national context is quite useful as well as the necessary language skills, particularly full English language literacy.

Deficient organizational capacities are oftentimes correlated with **lack of financial resources**. In terms of UBC, not all universities allocate sufficient funding for development and implementation of joint projects. A big difference in organizational capacities and available resources is evident between large and small universities. However, financial issues are more problematic on the SME side since universities often receive public funding and/or generate income themselves through other activities, such as education. SMEs perceive time and resource investment in preparation of joint projects, particularly for the EU grants, as high. They require lots of time and commitment from their side with small possibility of receiving the actual support. **Co-financing requirement in some grants is challenging for SMEs**. Even though the reasoning behind such approach is that SMEs will get some commercial benefit at end of or after the project, in reality, this to happen, usually takes a long period of time and additional investments from the company.

Finally, a problem that can exist in relation of any endeavor – **not enabling policy and regulatory environment** – has been identified in our research as an obstacle to HEI-SME collaboration. Foremost, the existing funding programs are predominantly geared towards large-scale industrial research, in which majority of SMEs and small universities cannot participate. This means that funding instruments are more attuned to the bigger companies and universities than smaller ones. Another barrier that was pinpointed is the fact that rapid research grants are non-existent. Such granting could enable HEIs and SMEs to make quick adjustments to novel developments in the field. Nevertheless, national differences in policy and regularly support are evident; while Germany, Ireland and France have UBC supportive systems, Spain, Finland and Cyprus experience greater structural barriers, which are also different between countries. Although Finland has fostered innovation, its HEIs are not proactive in fostering UBC like their German or Irish counterparts. Spain and Cyprus lack substantial public grant schemes for UBC and support for participation in European funded projects. France, Spain and Cyprus have restrictive and burdensome bureaucracies that determine how businesses can develop. For example, regulation in Spanish autonomous regions is sometimes not in line with the European policies. In general, the industrial and technological development differs greatly within countries, as large cities and their metropolitan regions experience greater growth and the overall UBC.

2.4. Support Mechanisms

The support mechanisms that are used by governments, businesses, and universities to support and drive UBC can be grouped into four categories: strategic, structural, operational and policy intervention mechanisms (Davey et al., 2011).

The strategic mechanisms can be divided in documented and implementation mechanisms. The first of these are documents such as the mission, vision, and strategy (Ssebuwufu et al., 2012). The second is the commitment to these documented strategies (Davey et al., 2018). This classification is mainly used for HEIs but can also be applied to businesses. For both HEIs and businesses, the strategy is based on their current future needs. Although the literature on strategies for businesses is limited, we can distinguish between two types of strategies (Bekkers & Bodas Freitas, 2008). These two types of strategies are those focused on the adoption of interdependent knowledge (through collaborative and contract research) and those focused on the adoption of systemic knowledge (through patents, licencing, etc.).

The structural mechanisms can be divided in three different types. First, the people-based mechanisms, such as board level position for UBC (Davey et al., 2011). Second, office/centre-based mechanisms, such as technology transfer offices (Markman, Gianiodis, Phan, and Balkin, 2004), or career offices (Davey

et al., 2011). Third, programme-based mechanisms, such as programmes facilitating interaction between HEI and industry (Ponomariov and Boarman, 2008).

The operational mechanisms are the practical actions that are taken to support UBC. These activities need to be aligned with the strategy of the organisation. The activities can be grouped into communication and exchange activities, linking and support activities, training and seminars, and information session and forums dedicated to the topics around UBC (Davey et al., 2018).

The policy or framework mechanisms are the economic and financial mechanisms, such as funding schemes, grants, subsidies, etc. (Harman, 2010), regulatory mechanisms, such as laws and regulations (Tartari and Breschi, 2012), and other mechanisms that are non-coercive, such as government programmes (Reynold et al., 2002). These mechanisms are not only important because they provide materials basis for UBC to take place, they also generate the overall development in certain sectors and move the

economy in a particular direction, especially if they are long term. This happens because the long term funding schemes showcase financial commitment. For example, the US provided a huge financial commitment through DARPA to create the Internet. Nowadays, the US gives financial commitment in the biotech system over decades. Such commitments create an environment in which people are willing to invest over a certain amount of time, not just financially, but even in terms of their careers.

GOOD PRACTICE

French tax incentives for hiring PhD students

Currently in France, UBC activities are powerfully driven by the tax incentives. Universities or engineering schools can place their PhD students in a firm to complete their study for three years. Later the firm continues to hire them as post-doctoral studies for another two years. The firm can get the money back in tax later on. These PhD and postdoctoral students work on very specific projects with limited scope (solve a very particular problem for the hiring company). The tax incentive has proven to foster UBC in France.

Table 1: Identified support mechanisms for UBC

Type	Mechanisms identified as the most useful for HEI&SME collaboration
Strategic mechanisms	<p>Strategic direction of the organization fosters UBC</p> <p>Regular strategic planning and foresight that enable organizations to adjust and reorient their research and operations to the social and market needs</p> <p>Communication and partnership strategies and action plans</p> <p>Top-level management team values and supports UBC and joint projects</p>

	HEIs commitment to R&D and actual support it offers to its researchers
Structural mechanisms	<p>Existence, scope and expertise of national-level industrial and technology development, knowledge/technology transfer agencies, and other bodies that directly enable UBC</p> <p>Existence, scope and expertise of knowledge/technology transfer offices, partnership departments, research departments, IP/legal support offices, finances, and similar (departments with larger staff and funding are more efficient)</p> <p>Hiring policies that favor people with UBC experience or work in different sectors</p> <p>Redesign of academic career profiles (adding UBC to research and teaching)</p> <p>Funding for UBC and development and implementation of collaborative projects</p> <p>Facilities for meetings, piloting activities, test centers, etc.</p> <p>Prizes, contests, awards and other mechanisms that promote excellence and best practice</p>
Operational mechanisms	<p>Boundary spanners: UBC mediators and experts with excellent communication skills</p> <p>Clear and direct UBC-related points of contacts at HEI</p> <p>Allowing designated employees contracted time to focus on developing collaborative projects</p> <p>Diverse informal and formal networking and matching events and channels</p> <p>Existence of long-term, continuous and reliable communication channels with established partners</p> <p>Fellowships, studentships, internships with companies</p> <p>Fairs, forums, committees, industrial days, meetings, conferences and other events¹⁰ (offline and online) that are frequent and diverse in nature and bring together HEI and SME representatives where success stories and good practices are shared¹¹</p> <p>Online UBC matching databases (on European level) with easy and user-friendly access, not only in R&D but also in prototype development</p> <p>Advertisement of UBC programmes on websites and ensuring online presence with case studies of good HEI-SME collaboration</p>

¹⁰ One interviewee finds that the information sessions organised by the European Commission are mostly attended by people from universities. Although it is difficult to tailor these webinars to diverse needs and topics, it would be useful to also have sessions focussed on the needs of SMEs and have grant offices participate as well.

¹¹ A suggestion was made for more frequent organisation of the European Industry Days by the European Commission (instead once a year, add smaller events throughout the year). Another suggestion is creation of an EU wide body/Committee, comprised of both HEIs and SMEs representatives that will be responsible to promote and disseminate UBC collaboration on an EU level, which will be connected to task force teams in each country to liaises with.

	<p>Development of protocols and manual for European projects, for example, protocols on subcontracting, financial management, etc.</p> <p>Free coaching services from initial project/initiative development to its implementation</p> <p>Seed funding on learning and practicing on how develop UBC and EU project proposals</p> <p>Support in monitoring and evaluation activities, including in performance of independent pre-assessments of the project proposal (for better chances of winning grants and improving their social and industrial impact)¹²</p> <p>Training and education in UBC and all support mechanisms listed here (flexible formats to adjust to schedules of HEI and SME stakeholders)</p> <p>Step by step instructions, guidelines and manuals on all UBC related programs</p>
<p>Policy mechanisms</p>	<p>Salary and other career development incentives that favor UBC and valorization</p> <p>National and international research excellence ranking indexes</p> <p>National and European funding grants and subsidies</p> <p>Incentives in positive evaluation of project proposals that incorporate SMEs and startups</p> <p>Regulations and administrative procedures that favor UBC and take into account SME realities, interests and modalities of work</p> <p>Schemes that support transdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research</p> <p>Schemes that support R&D and innovation</p> <p>Ensuring university-level funding for applying for EU projects</p> <p>Training on HEI-SME collaboration for advisors working in national economic development agencies</p> <p>Institutional and financial policies that enable hiring of consultancies in UBC and EU applications to help HEIs and SMEs to develop joint projects</p> <p>Straightforward and user-friendly administrative procedures at HEIs and national and European granting bodies</p>

¹² It is very important to make sure that what is agreed in the proposal will be implemented. It should be ensured that within HEIs there are no gaps in the resources needed for the project, that they are committed to doing the tests agreed on in the proposal, and that their facilities can be used for the project.

3. Key Competencies for HEI & SME Collaboration

The following chapter provides an overview of the key competencies for successful UBC focusing on HEIs and SMEs partnerships. The listed competencies reflect abilities and skills of successful collaborative managers which have been identified extensively in leaderships and management studies. Our research findings reflect those but explore competencies through our analytical focus, i.e. in the context of UBC issues and joint European funded projects. However, this chapter does not describe the actual skill base directly associated with competencies but rather elaborates on key issues that arise in UBC - whether in research, education or valorisation – that needs to be addressed well for partnerships and projects to be fruitful.

Figure 5: The most important skills and capabilities needed for successful collaboration in Horizon2020, Horizon Europe, or Erasmus+ projects, based on our survey results

Namely, the key success factor for all UBC initiatives and projects is the talented and competent staff on both sides. The human capital an organization possesses reflects its worth and potential progress. Considering the fast pace of socio-technological changes on one side, and the slow adaptation process of the academia and the public sector in general to these changes on the other, generate high demand for talent and expertise that cannot be found easily on the labour market.

Our research informants find that excellent academic record does not reflect actual professional capabilities. Training outside formal education becomes crucial, until majority of HEIs catch up and adapt their curriculums and methods to the high complexity and speed of change of the modern societies. Again, UBC is of vital importance here too, not just in research. Our research finds that competencies and fields of knowledge highlighted in this report are usually developed through substantial experience and direct involvement in project management, research, networking efforts and other life-real practice through which expertise has been developed. Therefore, any training in this field requires hands-on methods and applied knowledge. High-quality mentors should come from the field too, as they can transfer their skills in similar settings through which they pruned their expertise. Irrevocably, such training needs to be customizable and tailored to the needs of participants ("not too school-like") ensuring the commitment of businesses participants and other practitioners so it fits their busy schedules. The training should address other challenges, facilitators and motivations presented in this report.

Finally, another issues that needs to be emphasized is the relevance of soft, interpersonal and communication skills. Majority of our research informants mentioned empathy over and over again, as a competency that is greatly appreciate, needed and valued. This trait to be understand well others and oneself is closely related to the ability to listen to others, understand their needs and expectations, and to clearly share your own in an acceptable manner. This finding should not be surprising considering that the subject of our research focuses on collaborative endeavours. In this setting, decision-making revolves around other people, so having the skills to manage others is central to being a successful UBC practitioner, whether working in HEI, SME or elsewhere. Our interviewees find that achievements in this line of work is not about implementing projects perfectly, but rather having everybody on board.

Consortium Assemblage and Proposal Writing

Prerequisite for collaborative UBC research and networking projects is to conceptualize and write them. Usually larger HEIs have specialized departments and/or staff that support their academics and researchers in proposal writing and creation of the project consortium. Some universities engage external consultancies, sometimes SMEs to provide such services to their academics. However, many universities still lack to provide UBC related support and, in such cases, researchers are left on their own. Also, in

many instances SMEs emphasized how their companies lack expertise in writing project proposals but do not have the necessary time and resources to engage in development of those skills. Particularly the application process for establishing a European consortium can be quite long (~10 months) and the proposal are 50 pages long. This work is time consuming, requires expertise and social networking, i.e. requires staff that SMEs rarely have at disposal. In particular, European funded projects require allocation of extensive human resources and time for their development. Aside writing the project proposal, it is evident from research that finding trusting and competent project partners and building a good consortium is a big challenge, especially when such efforts are made on a regional or international scope.

Competency to develop winning project proposals requires not only in-depth understanding of funding instruments, but also understanding of collaborative team, project and time management, which all should be reflected in the project proposal and the division of roles and tasks. Our research informants emphasized how they learned a lot about development and running of such programs by making mistakes and trying to correct them later on. In particular, selection of partners in the initial UBC was oftentimes random (“creating a consortium blindly”) and was not scrutinized; however, after diverse experiences, consortium assemblage is evidently a crucial factor to many not only for successful completion of a project but for its social/industrial impact as well. Therefore, HEIs and SMEs that have experience in UBC and particularly on large-scale joint research projects tend to carefully consider their involvement in such projects and select competent partners. This is particularly challenging for international projects as many do not have established networks outside their home countries and are interested in learning more about potential partners abroad. Both sides in UBC are interested in finding serious and committed partners who are not engaged in collaboration solely for financial reasons and which will ensure timely and substantive implementation of joint activities. As noted earlier, the misalignment of objectives is often related to the main interests of both sides: while universities seek to commercialize theoretical results, companies want to generate prototypes. Needs of both sides should be met through UBC. Understanding the needs of

GOOD PRACTICE

The Innovation Voucher

The Innovation Voucher in Ireland initiative was developed to build links between Ireland's public knowledge providers (i.e. higher education institutes, public research bodies) and small businesses. Innovation Vouchers worth €5,000 are available to assist a company or companies to explore a business opportunity or problem with a registered knowledge provider. In an independent survey of companies that participated in the Innovation Voucher Programme 97% of respondents would be willing to recommend the Programme to other businesses.

each partner in the early stages of project/initiative development is crucial, especially for organizations that have not worked together earlier.

Another competency that was emphasized both by HEIs and SMEs is conceptualization of projects through which talent acquisition and hiring of staff is conducted, especially for longer periods of time. Shortage of experts, project managers and professionals with prior UBC experience is something that plagues most organizations in all country contexts that were investigated as part of our research. Thus, development of projects and seeking funding for acquiring such expertise and retaining people in organizations is highly desirable. Due to the natural time limitation of externally funded projects, being able to do that is not a straightforward thing. It requires ingenuity and managerial creativity in relating and sequencing projects and their activities.

In terms of project design, several interviewees find that successful project proposal development should result in identification of realistic project objectives that can be achieved in a limited timeframe. This fact is important not only for meeting funding requirements but also to avoid demotivation and frustration of involved project partners. Therefore, understanding capacities and competencies of involved partners, their mode of operations and adjusting project activities and outcomes to these realities is determinant of project's success. In order to establish a well-organized consortium, trust between involved parties should be in place. Trust is built on clear divisions

of work and belief that everybody will do their part to the best of their abilities. A good strategy in building a consortium is based on being aware of those lines of research and work in which each partner stands out and to only participate in those projects in which an organization can really provide differential value. If organizations do not have the staff or the necessary capacity, it is better to inform the other side and recommend another partner that can add value to the consortium.

Finally, our research participants expressed interest in building international collaboration and alliances beyond the European Union and are interested in finding partner organizations – HEIs and SMEs – in the Eastern Europe, the Western Balkans, Asia and United States. Novel grant schemes are emerging for such UBC and joint research to tackle global challenges and foster the knowledge transition between countries. Beside international partnerships, both HEIs and SMEs are interested in joining experienced

GOOD PRACTICE

The Irish Agile Innovation Programme

In this model an agency expert works with the company all through the process from initiation to project completion. This expert is selected based on their experience and area of expertise. Such approach to supporting UBC was selected because inexperienced HEIs and SMEs do not know where to start. By working with an expert, organizations are mentored throughout the UBC project initiation, design and later implementation phases.

UBC and Horizon 2020 organizations in new projects. This interest stems from the need to have good project references for proposals but also to learn from others who have more R&D experience.

In sum, most issues that come up during the project implementation can be avoided at the proposal writing stage or when entering the collaboration. Internal training offerings could support researchers in their understanding of the full context of collaboration in EU-funded projects, including the industry's perspective. Also, SMEs could benefit from practical support, including capacity building on better understanding what kind of funding programmes exist.

Project/Research Design for Industry and Social Impact

Considering the existing need to generate social change and meaningful impact, creating projects that actually are able to address pressing social and environmental problems through novel approaches and technological solutions is of high importance. Competency to put ideas on paper and structure projects and UBC initiatives to result in desired outcomes is extremely valued. It is important to stress that this competency differs from the general proposal writing competency, also described in this report, as the ability to design projects and research for impact highlights someone's in-depth understanding of issues at stake, their interconnections and how change should be addressed. Therefore, beside possessing knowledge of the technical or field related to the subject of the project or research, such in-depth understanding would include strong managerial and organizational aspects of how the knowledge production in that specific initiative/study should be structured. Thus, this competency underlines ability to understand needs, interests and values of all stakeholders alongside the technical expertise.

Our research shows that experts who possess such skills are rare. Namely, lots of interviewees shared their disappointment with the overall impact of UBC initiatives, and especially of European funded projects, i.e. the impact was not high as they initially expected. Reasons behind limited impact they assigned to inadequate design of the networking or research projects. Particularly, businesses and SMEs seek direct and immediate outcomes and successes and are frustrated by the long-term orientation of academia and the over slow pace of operations in most HEIs. SME representatives find that majority of academics lack this competency, particularly the ability to identify industrial and/or social impact.

Industrial and social impact of proposed initiatives and projects needs to be evident to the external audience as well, not just their developers. HEIs and SMEs have to explain their proposals in a small number of pages where they capture the crucial information that is sufficiently attractive on a technical level but also provides good insight into social impact for it to be accepted by the evaluation committee.

Ensuring social impact in the project design is important not just externally but works as an internal driving force for the project team as well. Since salaries in the public education systems are low and it is difficult to motivate academics with monetary incentives for UBC, one has to develop excellent projects of great quality with good impact to overcome this barrier. To do so, the UBC collaboration and especially European funded projects should be designed to ensure impact in the timespan they are envisioned for implementation.

To generate considerable impact in a limited timeframe, initiatives and projects have to be strategically focused on specific issues or targets. This means that good impact results from strong focus. The design of the Horizon Europe programs compared to those from the Horizon 2020 entails a strategic move towards objective driven research. This change has been positively evaluated by practitioners. In Horizon 2020 projects were allocated to excellent institutions and after the project implementors had to make the case that impact has been made. Based on their experience in participation in Horizon 2020 projects, such approach produced limited and not substantial or long-term benefits to involved organizations or the society. After the project ends, involved stakeholders are out of the game. The Horizon Europe has a reversed approach, focusing on objectives and potential impact.¹³

A good indicator of potential impact of an idea proposed in projects and initiatives is its potential to be applied in social and/or industrial practice. For example, when IT infrastructure is created, it should be clear from the outset how it will be used, by whom and for what purpose. Furthermore, social and business application of such infrastructure should be directly addressed. Part of such application in practice is consideration of costs. Solutions that are too expensive and cannot survive on the market due to its high costs should be carefully reconsidered. Especially for new technologies this factor should be considered in their development processes, otherwise researchers will produce solutions that are not marketable, too expensive and hence nobody can use them. Finally,

funding agencies should require the proposed projects and initiatives to validate market or real-life

GOOD PRACTICE

Testing solutions in real life practice and markets

An excellent way to ensure social and industrial impact of develop solutions is to test them on the market directly. LOTUS – a Horizon 2020 funded project in implementation by L'École Polytechnique and 23 partners organizations, including EASY GLOBAL MARKET SAS, SME company from France, is developing an innovative chemical sensor for water quality monitoring, which will be tested during the project in India.

¹³ The evaluation analysis of Horizon 2020 indicates mistakes in this program and the reasons why Horizon Europe was designed using a new approach that focuses on specific objectives: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/how-horizon-europe-was-developed_en

needs behind the idea more than they currently do. Letters for intent and memorandums of understanding are good tools for this.

From Idea to the Market: Negotiating Risks and Profits

A frequent problem that arises in collaboration between HEIs and businesses, and particularly with SMEs, is the conflicting interest of both sides on how risks and profits are to be shared. The rights arising from the UBC contract are sometimes not clear and it is difficult to determine who has what share in the results that are developed. HEIs or researchers often want compensation that is difficult to assess, as it is difficult to determine upfront what the profit will look like in the end. For successful UBC, negotiating well decision-making processes, property rights, profit and risk sharing is crucial. If these issues are not resolved properly or defined upfront, conflicts can arise, as our research shows. This issue is not important for one-time off projects or collaborations, but rather affects the whole UBC ecosystem. For example, in France the profit expectations of academic researchers are not realistic because they value their ideas and solutions development over commercialization processes; whereas business representatives think risks involved in commercialization

GOOD PRACTICE

Change 2020 portfolio model

Participants of Finnish INNOFOKUS project created the following "Change 2020" model on how portfolio-thinking and leveraging different funding instruments should be used. The model has three stages:

- 1) Proof of concept (domestic funding): In the first stage, universities and businesses experiment initial ideas in practice and do capability-building. Objective is to learn as much as possible. Experiments attract resources (networks, partners) behind the idea. Results of this first stage should be used to seek out international partners that makes it possible to apply for international R&D funding with a wider consortium.
- 2) World-class RDI (international funding): Second stage takes Finnish SME-HEI consortiums international. It connects Finnish participants with leading European research organizations and corporations; piloting new solutions across Europe; sourcing existing knowledge and combining it into new concepts.
- 3) Research to market (domestic & international private / public funding): Third stage is about valorization of the results - implementing the latest research knowledge and technologies into innovations with businesses as commercializers.

of such ideas and solutions is quite high and demanding and find that profits should reflect that fact. Such clashing standpoints hinder wider UBC expansion not just in single instances but for the whole economy. To determine what is fair to everybody is important as it sets the basis for development of rules and practices that can later be accepted and used as the norm.

An area where norms have not been set yet, and there is lots of disagreement about is the ownership of patent and data rights, which are related to the problem of how researchers are to be compensated for their valorisation work. Namely, the majority of academic researchers undertaking UBC do not feel properly compensated for their efforts. However, successful UBC initiatives find ways to create financial incentives for them by giving researchers financial contribution or shares directly from the company with which they collaborate or including them in the patent resulting from the project. However, in terms of patent sharing rights, when a joint venture or an alliance creates patents through collaboration, problems arise as to who owns what, how would the intellectual property be shared. This needs to be address up front and negotiated throughout the project. A similar problem arises in terms of data. Since lots of recent projects incorporate data generation, here are high expectations that in the future this data will be monetized. While it is difficult to predict in this which way and extent this will happen, due to this expectation conflict in interests take place because both sides want to own the data.

However, the conflict in interests does not arise just of incompatibility between what each side wants, as much as due to the misunderstandings and lack of knowledge about the other. Oftentimes, there are other incentives at work aside financial ones. Organizations that are successful in UBC have been able to negotiate not only profit and risk sharing but also other interests. They are able to understand what their partners want, what their interests are and what the partnership will give to the both sides. Therefore, establishing a standpoint on these aspects and considering stakes one gives to others in partnerships is important.

For HEIs, training of students is quite important. Universities that are successful in UBC approach it from the long-term perspective and rather receive smaller funding from projects but ask for intake of their students in companies for training, especially PhDs and post-doctoral students. On the other side, access to human resources through UBC is also attractive to companies, especially SMEs. These job on training raises both individual and organizational capacity by developing skills of the trainee as well as building the company in a resilient way.

Particularly student training is something that is more attractive to SMEs than research for example. The smaller the business, the more concrete its needs are. Start-ups and entrepreneur-driven companies often expect to find directly new customers, increased sales, visibility and other short-term benefits, which might be difficult to get in R&D joint-projects. For these long-term projects, ensuring funding is very important when SMEs are involved. The main problem of small companies is that they focus their attention on issue for a particular point in time. Their priorities and needs are changing very quickly, so research that takes long time to be prepared might not suitable for their needs, because by the time they receive it from their academic counterparts, they might have moved on to something new. As mentioned earlier, their timing and their horizon is not the same as in academic institutions. However, to keep SMEs focused and engaged, structured funding projects can provide the best framework. Although funding is important

for SMEs and this should be definitely incorporated in the proposals (as many SME informants in our research highlighted the problem of participation in projects without any compensation), one should keep in mind that the funding amounts play different roles for SMEs compared to HEIs. For example, 20.000 Euro may only make up for 20% of a project budget, but this amount might mean a lot for an SME.

Careful consideration of SME's financial involvement in UBC initiatives and projects should take place on case by case basis, depending on the actual role of SME and the funding framework. Firstly, an initial capital for applying and starting a consortium is needed even for a successful application. HEIs should have a separate budget for this purpose to ensure the accumulation and utilization of long-term experience. Secondly, some funding schemes cover only certain amount of project costs and in many cases, these costs are reimbursed later, which means the consortium has to pay by itself first. While the missing funding can be allocated from third sources or through generating income, in many instances investors will easily invest in research because they do not perceive it as a ready product. These issues should be considered up front when projects are designed.

Despite these challenges, some SMEs still are interested to be part of UBC research focused projects because it provides them with the insider knowledge and networking opportunities. While they cannot afford such endeavours on their own due to high costs, by being part of large consortiums they can directly participate and have strategic information and contacts.

Therefore, when UBC entails partnerships with SMEs, their partners have to be aware that much of the preparatory work needs to be done by HEIs. When universities or their intermediaries responsible for building the consortium have done their homework well - understood the needs of their potential partners, put together the consortium and drafted a project plan that shows clear research and educational benefits for HEIs and business impact for SMEs - it's easier to get everyone onboard. Particularly, property rights need to be carefully considered alongside everyone's needs from their scientific, educational or business viewpoints. By understanding the differences in roles and goals, a common state of mind for forming a consortium can also be found.

Informal and Formal Networking

Since UBC entails coalition building, the ability to network informally and formally is central in processes of initiating, designing and implementing initiatives and projects which bring together HEIs and businesses. This means that only you have to find a *partner*, you foremost need to identify *the right partner*. One needs to **find and connect with the right people** - ones you can trust and can get things done. To find them, you need social capital and networks that

GOOD PRACTICE

Martel Innovate success strategy: The power of people

When building a partnership, the main input on which Martel relies is the power of people and personal connections that are a key pillar for business development and acquisition, as well as for the development of strategic alliances. Each Martel employee is an ambassador and a multiplier via their network of contacts. This is how Martel gets contacted frequently also by third parties that heard about the work, attention to quality and excellence at all levels and successes record of Martel. There is a sort of snowball effect triggered by good reviews and recommendations from current and former clients. In addition, an important acquisition channel for Martel is the events organized or attended: ideal venues to make new connections and trigger collaborations.

can introduce you to new contacts. Although **online presence** is helpful, relying on this form of communication does not bring significant benefits. While it is important to showcase credibility and excellent in online media, oftentimes, information on the Internet and websites is confusing and especially it is difficult to pinpoint the potential of new knowledge and technologies and to establish trust crucial for building relationships. Even **intelligent matching databases** cannot overcome the human need for real interaction. Our research informants unremittingly emphasized **the feet on the street approach**. Getting to know the local business and research community and becoming a key part of the economic ecosystem in the region an organization operates in is the key. One has to be proactive in informal and formal networking and use different communication channels while keeping in mind that establishing personal connections is the best option.

Seminars, conferences, workshops, forums, science parks and other type of events that bring together experts, professionals and researchers from different fields are quite useful. HEIs can take a proactive role and organize high-quality seminars themselves and invite the business community. In fact, in European funded projects, the initial communication and coalition building oftentimes starts through **research networks** that are created by academics working in certain fields and attending the same academic events. These networks involve lots of communication and trust-building between organizational partners and can be extended to involve business partners. For example, the JAMK University of Applied Sciences in Finland used a *customer jury method* which involved inviting shortlisted businesses to present their pitches for potential new joint-projects and to receive feedback.

Beside establishing new contacts, organizations successful in UBC take significant effort in keeping and **nurturing their established networks**. Such HEIs usually have departments that are dedicated to partnerships, but commitment comes also from the top-level management too who actively participate in building coalitions. In this instance, **alumni networks** have been of high importance for UBC, particularly in France.

Involving students in all types of UBC

is important, not just for their training, but to generate new motivation, insights and ideas.

Nowadays lots of **UBC intermediary organizations** exist, from funding agencies, chambers of commerce to specialized consultancies. These can be particularly useful for international cooperation since contact and trust are lower in such settings, and having intermediaries making an introduction between organization is useful. Funding agencies and specialized UBC fostering bodies at the national and local level (cities, provinces, etc.) have become particularly valuable because in addition to active matchmaking and connecting their members into emerging consortiums, they provide information on various funding opportunities and programs, or give out support schemes themselves. In Ireland, the key UBC support is provided by the enterprise centre managers who focus on innovation and are on the lookout for innovation driven clients.

In sum, increasing personal and organizational social capital through new contacts, fostering existing interpersonal relationships, finding shared goal and mutual understanding is the most important driver and prerequisite for any type of UBC initiative or project.

GOOD PRACTICE

Personalized communication for UBC at the University of Montpellier

The Innovation & Partnerships department developed their Customer Relationship Management Plan to know better not only companies they cooperate with but also people behind it. So, they follow and build on existing and earlier relationships with their business partners. Their approach is personalized communication, which is time-consuming and requires special set of skills. Each year the University has 200 new business partners, and since it is difficult to communicate regularly with all of them, the team selects the most important partners based on the following priorities: i) company is a university spinoff, ii) company is based on university campus (there are cca 30 such companies), iii) company has lots of researchers employed, etc. The University President sends letters to these companies each year.

Collaborative Working Environments and Team Management

UBC initiatives and projects entail work in highly collaborative environments. Oftentimes, research and other activities are of participatory nature. Competency to efficiently manage teams, therefore, is quite important. Particularly the large European funded projects bring large number of organizations together, from different disciplines, sectors and backgrounds to work together. This can be quite challenging as organizations have different time orientation, procedures and capacities, as explained in earlier chapters of this report. In many cases, HEIs take the lead role in managing such projects, whereas they have to organize not only the work externally towards their partners but also internally with their departments and different disciplines. Even this internal management can be quite challenging as many schools have parallel functioning bodies and independent administration. For example, business schools in France are usually autonomous organizations loosely tied to some universities.

When UBC initiatives and projects are designed well, then roles and tasks should be clearly set out and divided properly. Nevertheless, regular communication between all partners is important to ensure adherence to deadlines, quality of outputs and buy-in of everybody involved. This collaborative management are usually in hands of project managers and coordinators. In comparison to other projects, UBC oftentimes involved cocreation activities, transdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches which often rely on design on new methods and ways of doing things. In such cases, project manager is rather a spanning boundary-agent, they are innovation directors and curators. Professionals in these roles take care of procedures but also content and act as mediators between different worlds, disciplines, stakeholders and ignite innovation, which is actually fostered by continuous learning and creativity. As such, the standard project portfolios need to be organized and adjusted to the these participatory cocreation processes. For example, Metropolia in Finland in their joint R&D projects incorporate open dialogue and collaboration with regional developers and local R&D actors through an ongoing "start-up roundtable" discussions.

To successfully manage UBC initiatives and projects, such collaborative managers needs to have specialized education and training. In reality, opportunities for such training are rare and usually professionals who possess such skills have acquired those through experience by working in diverse fields, roles and sectors. They should have in-depth understanding of how universities, businesses, including SMEs operate and, as such, can recognise research, business and technical needs of all stakeholders. It is also important for organizations to such managers sufficient institutional decision-making power so they can adjust procedures and teams to their co-creative management work and outputs. Organizations that give out such support, they recognize the need for transdisciplinary and co-creative work within their strategic approach alongside fostering open and collaborative organizational culture and the hiring policies that reflect hiring of staff that can lead such processes. Even facilities at such organizations enable interaction and collaborative workspaces between researchers, business professionals, students

and others. These can take place in online settings too, such through exchange platforms, since the pandemic situation has pushed everybody to move lots of their work online. While face-to-face interactions are important, when circumstances do not allow for it, then online platforms should be put in place to substitute continuous communication.

This communication should reiterate shared objectives and keep everybody on the track to their joint targets. Considering that organizations have their own ongoing operations and agendas, UBC managers have to ensure that their initiatives and projects have been properly integrated into organizational structures. Particularly SMEs focus on their profit generating activities and can

GOOD PRACTICE

Project Booster

This is a 3-month RDI project accelerator, in which cross-organizational teams identify, design and create a joint-project plan for submission. Project Booster aims increase the level of collaboration across universities and businesses; the quality of joint project plans; and simultaneously increase the number of staff members and business partners working with RDI projects. Project Booster was originally implemented by 3AMK strategic alliance of three universities of applied sciences in Helsinki Metropolitan area - Haaga-Helia, Laurea and Metropolia. It has been since also used by CLIC Innovation Ecosystem.

lose focus due to their constant adaptation processes. Managing projects that everybody stays committed requires technical and interpersonal ingenuity. While good collaboration entails clear definition and division of responsibilities of each partner, ensuring that there are no overlaps, redundancies and miscommunication; an excellent collaboration fosters complimentary combination of knowledge in expertise in all aspects of UBC project. Moreover, our research indicates that successful UBC results in a deeper familiarity of involved partners with each other, which later oftentimes results in new projects and opportunities. In this way, this collaborative learning process is combined with increasing interpersonal connections. In fact, beside the aforementioned UBC related abilities, many interviewees highlight the interpersonal skills such managers should possess. In combination to excellent communication abilities, they should showcase commitment and motivation, high level of professionalism, and be honest and emphatic with others. Since the relevance of the interpersonal skills was emphasized throughout our research, we dedicated a chapter on these competencies in this report.

Finally, another issue that was stressed out by our research informants is the fact that people with excellent UBC competencies, and in general in collaborative management, are hard to find on the market. Moreover, their training takes place oftentimes on the job, meaning they adopt UBC competencies while working on projects and initiatives. Investment in their training is thus long and substantial. Organizational capacity and willingness to retain such talent and excellent managers for indefinite periods of time and keep the expertise in house, raises the overall UBC capacity of institutions.

Currently, such managers are hired on projects for limited timeframes. When they leave, knowledge and skills are lost too. Since salaries in HEIs are low compared to other sectors, hiring later experienced UBC managers is difficult. HEIs oftentimes hire PhD students to manage projects without prior experience and learn on the job, which affects project implementation. Although HEIs can use their earlier employees as network contacts for new partnerships who are later hired in business and other sectors on better paid positions, addressing the role of UBC managers institutionally in terms of hiring and career advancement incentives would be beneficial for long-term organizational growth, particularly of HEIs.

Time and Project Management

This chapter is closely related to the previous chapter, as collaborative work and team management are tightly connected to the overall project management. The reason why these are separate is to highlight two different, but very relevant, aspects of project management referring to UBC: collaboration and time. While the previous chapter focuses on collaborative aspects of UBC projects, this chapter emphasizes the time element of such endeavors. Namely, since different stakeholders are involved in such projects, with differing operational procedures and overall time horizons, as explained in earlier chapters of this report, the project management in this instance has to carefully incorporate the time element. UBC managers, therefore, need to understand how much time is really needed by different partners to complete certain tasks, and include time for implementation of participatory activities, since collaborative work oftentimes involves feedbacks.

Another aspect of time management in collaborative environments, is the actual time people and organizations can and are willing to devote to the specific UBC initiative or project. This means that it is not only important to know how long an activity will take to get implemented, but also how long involved people are ready to devote their time to that activity. This understanding underlines the ability to comprehend the subjective timeframes for activities. This fact was highlighted in the French context and referred as “la temporalité”.

Due to the fact that oftentimes UBC managers lead several projects, their ability to properly time and align activities, and possibly generate reinforcing elements between them and project, should be greatly valued. This ability not only ensures timely implementation of projects and adherence to donors’ requirements, it saves organizational resources and supports other people involved in projects. Aligning activities and people in them calls for good coordination skills and general understanding and previous experience in doing them.

An important but often not treasured task in project management is report writing. External funding donors require these reports, which oftentimes are lengthy and detailed. Competency to prepare such reports is important as it ensures meeting funding obligations and progression of projects. It also entails financial reporting and guaranteeing funds are spent in accordance with adopted plans and sometimes being able to adapt to the arising needs.

Finally, the managerial role includes responsibility to ensure implementation of all milestones in the UBC project or initiative not just formally but substantially. In several cases our interviewees expressed disappointment related to the fact that some projects they were part of did not result in impact they hoped for and find that managers need to foster solvency and impact of projects in their financial but also technical terms. To do so, monitoring and evaluation should take place continuously alongside incorporating lessons learned from them into subsequent activities.

Interpersonal and Communication Skills

Competency to lead collaborative teams and network are directly related to person's interpersonal and communication skills. In fact, most competencies described in this report are in some way interrelated with interpersonal or communication skills. Although these skills differ and entail specific abilities, we have joined them here together because in practice one needs to master both to successfully initiate and lead UBC. In particular, the interpersonal skills were highlighted over and over in our qualitative research calling for us to pay special attention to these. Our expert interviewees emphasized the following abilities:

- Empathy
- Honesty
- Commitment
- Self-motivation
- Patience
- Openness and transparency
- Active listening
- Adaptability
- Self-initiative
- Negotiation
- Conflict-resolution/mediation

- Resilience and perseverance
- Optimism.¹⁴

Possessing these abilities translates into high-level professionalism, which is based on good social and emotional intelligence. It is evident that collaborative initiatives and projects, such as UBC, will require such skill set, especially as they generate great level of trustworthiness in others, which is crucial for teamwork. Namely, people who are empathic, honest and committed develop trust in others. Also, patience, active listening, commitment, and self-motivation showcase that a person is reliable and responsible, i.e. that it will get things done. Another perspective on the interpersonal competencies is that people who have those in place handle projects from a human-centric approach. They can manage expectations of others involved and ensure that everybody will know what they will get out UBC. In situations where only the lead organization and its project manager tells others what needs to be done, balance and sense of ownership is lost, as well as potential for co-creation. Ultimately, the collaborative team environment requires a lot of negotiation and mediation since conflict of different sorts constantly arise. Project manager with high interpersonal competencies can resolve those effectively.

In close connection to interpersonal competencies are communication skills. They sort of build on each other. Good communication skills are based on understanding the input information, asking for clarifications if necessary, and ability to send back information in an adequate and simple way so that the interlocutor understands it perfectly. Only in settings where open and continuous communication is in place, beneficial relationships can be built, both internally within the project team and involved partners, and externally, towards different project stakeholders and new contacts. Excellent communication fosters exchange of ideas, opinions, learning, support and overall team synergy which enables everybody to work well with each other. Occasionally, setbacks happen, and expected results did not take place, and especially in those situations, fostering communication in a productive way is important as it supports team resilience.

Finally, communication towards external stakeholders and different audiences is quite important for visibility and impact. This fact was mentioned in interviews and experts find that public outreach should be carefully integrated into project management and when necessary assigned to a specialist in the field. Using diverse communication tools, including written and video materials, is useful as it reaches different populations and generates new contacts and network formations.

¹⁴ These interpersonal skills closely reflect those presented in the recent report published by the McKinsey Global Institute "[Defining the skills citizens will need in the future world of work](#)" based on research by Marco Dondi, Julia Klier, Frédéric Panier, and Jörg Schubert.

Cultural and Foreign/English Language Skills

Implementation of international UBC initiatives, especially those funded by the European Union, necessitates foreign culture and language skills that will ensure proper communication and collaboration. Lack of professionals with excellent English language skills is more prominent in certain countries, such as Spain. However, the need for people who have experience in working in different country contexts and are able to adjust UBC activities to these different cultural norms is mentioned in all countries which were part of our research. Local contexts and working styles vary from one country to another. One needs to orientate oneself to those working with - whether it's bureaucratic French or top-to-bottom Germans. Particularly in community engagement having the cultural awareness in mind, and preparing activities in accordance, should be mastered.

Although cultural differences are apparent, rarely they are properly addressed in project design and implementation since projects oftentimes entail generalization of activities and outcomes. However, addressing these barriers heads on is very useful, as our research indicates, as problems that arise are time and money consuming. Sometimes it takes a long time in resolving them and costs UBC partners a lot of effort to find adequate solutions. Perhaps because culture is so deeply entrenched to our ways of living and working, people are not aware of how it greatly affects them. Raising cultural competencies through training and education can be quite useful and can be integrated into UBC or offered by external consultancies.

Applying for Funding

Implementation of UBC initiatives and projects usually requires internal or external funding. Especially costs of educational and joint R&D projects can be quite high as it involves high-level experts and expensive technologies. Moreover, in certain instances funding can act as a driver for UBC by fostering partnership building for innovation, as described in earlier chapters of this report. Applying for any kind of funding is quite competitive and challenging. Funding applications are usually long and take considerable time and effort to be prepared with uncertainty of being evaluated as successful for actual support. This makes the application process arduous for many. Furthermore, project proposal writing requires a special skillset and in-depth understanding of the funding body requirements, objectives and the operational language. Majority of funding bodies utilize different application formats and processes. Considering the limited time academics and SME professionals have at disposal, it is quite challenging for them to allocate time for preparation of project proposals or development of this skill.

Figure 6: How attractive for applying are the following European-level funding opportunities (Horizon Europe) - (%)

Particularly the European funding can be challenging due to its application process. To be successful in applying for such grants, organizations in a consortium need to know in detail, step by step, how a proposal is written and further implemented in Horizon Europe. They need to know how to develop the breakthrough idea, how to get feedback from policymakers on that idea, how to collaborate to establish a consortium, and how to involve an external evaluator. Beside understanding the European taxonomy, to develop a good proposal one must balance the funding criteria and the quality.

Despite the challenge, the European funding remains very attractive and continues to increase because it allocates large grants for long-term projects and extensive projects and initiatives that are otherwise very difficult to fund. Horizon Europe is a very attractive program due to the 100% funding rate and overhead rate of 25%, in contrast to a 7% overhead rate in other European funding programs. This results in a high amount of applications which make the program highly competitive.

Particularly for smaller universities and SMEs application for European funding can be challenging. Since the application process is resource intensive, smaller organization usually do not have specialized staff for such tasks. However, two factors have been helpful in supporting greater involvement of SMEs in European funded projects recently. The simplification of the application process for EU funding in recent years has made it much easier to apply. The other supporting mechanism is the requirement to have

certain number of SMEs included in the consortium. Thus, HEIs and their intermediaries take the lead role in preparing such applications and forming the consortium.

Figure 7: The thematic focus for applying in European-level (Horizon Europe) programmes - (%)

Beside these support mechanisms various others have been developed to encourage development of funding proposals, both in numbers and quality. National contact points for European research programmes are helpful and those interested in EU-funded projects can use their services. On occasions, these organize matchmaking meetings which make it easier to find suitable partners and build a consortium. Particularly, intermediary organizations with prior experience in applying for different granting schemes are the most helpful to companies and HEIs along this journey. Namely, our research finds that a proven strategy to support HEI-SME consortium is to have excellent experts on European funding applications on board, who can transform the people in the consortia through training and adjust to the proposal for a specific call for the Horizon Europe. These experts will support consortiums in developing winning grant applications and implementing sustainable funded projects with impact.

Namely, the funding application process entails not only the writing part but different aspects that need to be properly addressed to result in submitting a potentially successful application. Firstly, all involved organizations in a consortium need to find a suitable call. For example, the Horizon Europe entails various calls with different objectives and structure. Ability to read a call and to find the best fitting one is especially important as the language used can often be complicated. Secondly, understanding the eligibility criteria and the documentation needed for the application is the next step. Thirdly, organizations should clearly understand how implementation takes place from in terms of administrative and budget procedures. A useful insight into these aspects are results and experiences of other organizations involved in similar projects and funding schemes. In general, a lack of availability of results from previously implemented projects is reported. Also, by sharing their experiences in funding schemes,

organizations can foster learning and networking with new partners. For European level funding, knowing what issues can come up during the application and the later implementation process can save a lot of time and effort for HEIs and SMEs, but also generate better UBC outcomes. In this instance, insights into how reporting, documentation, billing, HR planning, deadlines, procurement and other procedures take place on certain grants is emphasized as beneficial throughout our research. For example, an issue with the billing process on EU funded projects seems to cause difficulties for SMEs as it is different to the regular business billing and requires either training of staff or involvement of controllers who have that expertise.

Figure 8: Expressed interest in support activities regards to applying for European-level programmes

Although various support mechanisms exist, many HEIs and particularly SMEs are not aware of those. Informing and searching for support also involves time, which many do not readily at disposal. Therefore, even training in how to look for funding opportunities and where to find them would be useful. This includes training on how to use different EU online platforms too.

Marketing and Pitching Research and Technologies

An important element of joint research and development (R&D) projects is production of novel research and technologies. Explaining why such solutions are needed is part of any funding applications. Even for non-research or product-based projects, such as networking or mobility UBC initiatives, justification of the need for a particular activity is a standard element of any proposal. This justification should showcase clear connection between why something is needed and what is to be done to address that need. In this way, need assessment in the justification should address potential impact of the proposed solution. Considering the existing need to generate social change and meaningful impact, creating projects that actually are able to address pressing social and environmental problems through novel approaches and technological solutions is of high value. However, this fact needs to be effectively shared with external stakeholders, especially the funding bodies. The industrial and social impact of the proposed UBC and its outcomes should be clearly illustrated in a limited space in combination with the technical aspects of the initiative or project.

Since project proposals are limited (for example, for EU funded projects, in 70 pages for Horizon 2020 and now 50 pages for Horizon Europe) one has to produce clear, concise text that showcases impact. These proposals include summaries and pitch sections. Interviewees shared their experiences of cases where academics send several research papers and lots of materials, unable to produce concise pitch text and define potential industrial or social impact of the research they are working on. This problem arises due to the fact that in everyday lives of academics, they are not asked to continuously demonstrate social impact of their research, and hence, the need to develop such skills is quite low. In some conferences, during poster sessions, PhD students have 3 minutes to present and pitch their research and this approach is a good training rather than having academics present their papers for 15 to 30 minutes. The skill of pitching and communicating research is quite important but many academics lack it.

Strategic Planning and Foresight

Development of partnerships between HEIs and SMEs and any other form of UBC should be carefully tied to the processes of their organizational development. For organizations that are successful in UBC, selection of partners is not random and is carefully considered and planned. Such organizations question how a specific collaboration helps them on a longer term in relation to their growth and also to create meaningful and impactful solutions. Therefore, their strategic orientation is not about quick wins but rather long-term internal and external impact.

One aspect of that external strategic outlook is organizational adaptation to the socio-economic and technological realities. To follow these realities, one needs to survey specific fields and communities of knowledge. Sometimes involvement in UBC can provide that strategic insight which otherwise might have been difficult or costly to gain. Also, national, European and global level policies and adjunct funding are based on strategies of leading governmental and research stakeholders which provide insight into their short- and long-term objectives. The importance of aligning organizational directions to those objectives was emphasized by our research informants. For example, a wave of 5G-healthcare-related funding is emerging at a national level in France generating novel UBC between engineering and medical schools on one side and businesses on the other. Also, strategies should allow for faster alternations of direction within organizations as the social and especially market realities rapidly change.

These rapid changes are caused by the level of experimentation in the society and support such efforts receive, including funding. Such experimentation involves ground-breaking projects which pursue substantial impact on the social and the industrial world. Involvement in such projects is quite attractive to HEIs but SMEs as their successes create major long-term effects on their organizational development and business growth. This aspect is opposed by another internal strategic aspect of UBC, which calls for continuity. While projects and initiatives are implemented in specific timeframes, meeting challenging goals tied to the social or industrial impact requires long-term commitment over decades. In this instance, new UBC should result in building on existing accomplishments and ensure continuity between projects in meeting their connecting objectives.

4. Key Fields of Knowledge for HEI & SME Collaboration

This chapter describes briefly different fields of knowledge and specific expertise that was highlighted during our research. The fields of knowledge and expertise it entails are somewhat different from the previous competencies because they entail specific disciplines to be considered alongside the training. This means that the earlier competencies are rather managerial traits that any UBC expert should foster, while the fields of knowledge require longer mastery and usually involves specialization. While training in all these fields is useful for UBC managers to have since it can provide them with insight into how fields operate and around which themes they revolved, inclusion of high-level experts from these fields still would be beneficial for UBC initiatives and projects, and should be considered when UBC consortiums are designed and created.

R&D and Innovation

Research and development (R&D) are activities that focus on the innovation of new technologies, products, services or methods. The drive for valorization of research calls for stronger roles of researchers as developers and innovators. However, the formal education still lags behind the processes of upskilling academics for these new roles. Training and support in R&D and innovation processes would be helpful not only for professionals from technical and natural fields of study, but also from social sciences and humanities. Learning how the innovation processes start and are implemented, how prototyping, testing and validation of solutions is conducted, as well as learning to use different road mapping tools and how to valorize or commercialize various R&D products would highly benefit HEIs to foster translation of fundamental knowledge into applied research. These insights would be useful for SMEs too as many of them do not have R&D components unless they are research-oriented businesses themselves.

Multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinarity

A novel aspiration in natural and social sciences, as well as in humanities, is integration of scientific discoveries across different disciplines, fields of knowledge and methods. In fact, the complex nature of the physical and social reality calls for a different approach to solving problems – one that yields insights of its multifaced aspect from different analytical angles and tools. At the same time, the technological developments offer incorporation of social and technical domains and deeper understanding of empirical facts based on massive data collection. Despite this progress, scientific integration is not a straightforward process. It requires improvements in interdisciplinary methods and stronger and iterative

linkage between the theory and the practice. Our research results indicate that successful UBC offers precisely that: new knowledge and technologies stemming out of transdisciplinary or multidisciplinary collaborations. Vertical domains, such as precision agriculture, waste management, marine biology, or any domain which combines field knowledge with technological expertise, especially in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and robotics, seek to create unique solutions to existing issues. Such solutions require multidisciplinary teams and methods, yet universities still remain divided between disciplines. Although some researchers and professionals are open to diverse disciplines, in reality, majority of HEIs remain compartmentalized organizations into departments and units. Beside the world-leading technological universities that have realized the need to integrate their different disciplines into major groups (natural, technological and social sciences) by offering continuous interaction between them, most HEIs and the higher education system in general provide small incentives for academics and researchers from different disciplines to actually collaborate. On the other hand, SMEs find that multidisciplinary or transdisciplinary approaches should be the norm, as they allow teams to address issues from multitude of analytical angles and develop solutions to problems as they arise.

Multidisciplinarity involves studying a research topic in not just one discipline but in several at the same time. Any topic will ultimately be enriched by the incorporation of the perspectives of several disciplines. The multidisciplinary approach overflows disciplinary boundaries, but its goal remains limited to the framework of disciplinary research (Nicolescu, 2014). Interdisciplinarity concerns the transfer of methods from one discipline to another. Like multidisciplinarity, interdisciplinarity overflows disciplines, but its goal

GOOD PRACTICE

Co-Creation Platforms in Finland

Finish co-creation platforms in act as facilitators and boundary spanners, who support long-term interaction and culture-building across organizations. Great example of a co-creation platform is [Urban Mill](#) - a space, a community and a service situated in at the heart of Aalto University campus in Espoo, Finland. Operating a Public-Private-People-Partnership model, the "producers" of Urban Mill work to benefit the whole of the surrounding area. In their daily work, they promote and facilitate collaboration between quadruple helix actors to create, prototype, validate and test new products and services in real-life conditions. Urban Mill has organized and facilitated hundreds events since its inception in 2014. Urban Mill uses the word "orchestration" to describe their role as co-creation platform.

[Metropolia University of Applied Sciences](#) established collaboration platforms as innovation hubs with facilities, skills and joint-projects. Platforms are locations where a lot of R&D with businesses and stakeholders takes place. Re-organization of R&D activities around thematic innovation hubs (as opposed to traditional study fields) required multidisciplinary input from academics and R&D experts.

still remains within the framework of disciplinary research. (Nicolescu, 2014). Transdisciplinarity concerns that which is at once between the disciplines, across the different disciplines, and beyond all disciplines. Its goal is the understanding of the present world, of which one of the imperatives is the unity of knowledge. (Nicolescu, 2014).

The ability to develop and lead research projects of multidisciplinary or transdisciplinary nature has been identified as an important individual and organizational competency, particularly for HEI counterparts. At the same time, it is quite difficult for organizations to find such experts. Competencies in transdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary research should be fostered through formal and non-formal education and training.

Intellectual Property Rights (IP)

As explained in the chapter which deals with competency on risk and profit sharing, definition of rights and obligations between involved parties is highly important. These entail legal aspects out of which the intellectual property rights (IP) are crucial. The use of patents, software, databases, and other tangible tools which results out of UBC projects, needs to be addressed in the project to ensure their access and usage. This aspect is not only important for commercialization, i.e. who will further develop the product or the service and gain financial benefits and in what way, but effective delineation of property rights ensures the social or industrial impact of the UBC project and sustainability of project results. These issues should be resolved at the beginning of a project or ideally during the consortium assemblage.

Liability is another issue that oftentimes needs to be addressed in terms of projects and requires legal expertise to be handled properly. Also, confidentiality issues should be addressed. Namely, oftentimes funding requires research and outcomes to be publicly shared, while companies see this as conflict to their business interest. This fact may make companies hesitant to involve themselves in public research. However, the European level funding includes mechanisms to ensure sensitive results are kept private, and training on these mechanisms would be useful.

GOOD PRACTICE

Innovation Spaces for UBC

MERITS is an innovation thinkspace hub created to support digital and technology innovation in the Mid-East region of Ireland (Kildare, Meath and Wicklow). Their building is spread over 1200sqm and equipped with latest tools and technologies to provide their members with necessary resources for development. Beside academics and researchers, the hub brings together businesses and chambers of commerce and generates direct UBC linkages.

While larger HEIs usually have specialized legal departments for this kind of work, many smaller universities and SMEs lack legal support for UBC. Templates for IP issues provided by the European level funding bodies are useful, but still training in using those would be helpful.

Emerging Technologies

While emerging technologies is not field in itself, many of our research informants shared their interested in training in different emerging technologies. Considering the pace of technologies changes, the need to learn about the new solutions and products in constantly there. Particularly the application of IT in vertical domains has made it possible for tremendous innovation and calls for constant learning. The list of emerging technologies is constantly expanding.¹⁵

Learning opportunities about emerging technologies exist but are rare. Mainly through specialized research groups or conferences one can learn about the potential impact of certain discovering, but these might be difficult to access for many. Also, certain universities, especially research oriented HEIs, hold specialized public conferences on emerging technologies promoting their departments, research and also making connections to business through such venues.¹⁶

Technology Foresight: Discoveries at an Early Stage

Closely related to the previous field is the technology foresight which is a novel field in itself. This field seeks to make a connection between new discoveries in fundamental science and potential for the applied research. Interpretation of this potential oftentimes leads into strategies, policies and later on funding. Particularly for SMEs having access to information on discoveries in their early stages would be useful as it provides them with strategic information on which they can leverage their business ideas and products. UBC initiatives and projects can revolve around such exchanges and valorisation or experimentation.

EU Green Policies

Alongside technologies, the drive to address environmental issues, particularly the climate change, has been translated into top-level strategic and policy platforms on the European and national level.

¹⁵ For example, see the [List of emerging technologies on Wikipedia](#): or the World Economic Forum's [Report on the Top 10 Emerging Technologies of 2020](#).

¹⁶ See, for example, [MIT's EmTech Conference for 2021](#).

Consequently, HEIs and SMEs are interested in developing sustainable solutions when proposing their UBC initiatives and projects not only in environmental sciences, but basically in all industries and fields. Especially the EU Green Deal has made a strategic impact onto different European policies and has been a powerful dynamic behind development of green economy solutions. The EU environmental regulation also fosters research and UBC as it requires novel solutions. Also, these European policies have trickled down to national strategies and funding, if not already being there in place. These developments seek more extensive training and education in EU Green policies from both sides, HEIs and SMEs, which are interested to learn more how to incorporate the green elements into their work and projects.

Citizen Science

Citizen science entails participation of citizens and the general public in scientific research. Such participation takes place through crowdsourcing and or direct involvement of citizens, businesses and other stakeholders in research. It invites these stakeholders to take part in scientific discoveries not solely as beneficiaries but as co-creators. The focus of citizen science is oftentimes on applied knowledge and finding solutions to real-world problems. Due to the increased amount of easily accessible knowledge and technologies nowadays, the knowledge production takes place outside academia too, oftentimes by practitioners themselves. For example, an agriculture ecosystem in France has been developed gathering lots of farmers, SMEs and citizens interested in these issues who perform research themselves and learn to apply technical solutions through YouTube videos.

GOOD PRACTICE

Citizen science in agriculture in France

Through a knowledge sharing platform,
<https://www.verdeterreprod.fr>
farmers and SMEs aim to foster their own learning and define market solutions that would be useful and immediately applicable.

Although is true that knowledge and technologies are more accessible, at the same time, access to major research, technologies and information in general is limited to the public. In general, a movement exists that seeks to collect as much as possible information and share it openly. These initiatives can be described as even counterculture as they grow through social networks (another example from France is www.landfiles.fr).

The fact that such initiatives have developed showcases also the remoteness of academic research from everyday industry and social needs. Our research informants find that lots of research produced in academic does not relate to the actual social or market needs or does not reach the actual beneficiaries.

Like businesses, HEIs should be aware of the needs, interests and opinions of its customers, citizens. Development of projects that have strong citizen science component would generate greater social impact of its outputs, while incorporating UBC would ensure knowledge sharing and valorisation, as many SMEs acquire insights through the aforementioned citizen knowledge networks and/or follow market trends. The European Commission also supports Citizen science programs.

Open Science

Open science is movement and also set of norms that seek to increase openness, integrity, and reproducibility of academic research. As such, it is closely related to the notion of Citizen science in aspect of its openness, as the main objective of Open science is to make scientific information, data and outputs more widely visible and accessible. Other aspects of the Open science norms are to make research more rigorous by applying reproducibility as one of its standards in an open manner. Finally, integrity and ethical aspects of scientific research should be carefully taken into consideration. Open science standards have to be taken into consideration from the outset of research, during its design, since standards apply to each research phase, from defining research hypotheses to dissemination and reuse of research outputs. The European Commission in its funding is largely building its funding requirements on the Open science norms. These aspects are of interest to HEIs and SMEs as they would like to improve their joint research and dissemination in this regard.

GOOD PRACTICE

EU Open Science

Through its web platforms [Open Science Policy](#) and [Open Science Monitor](#), the European Commission supports open science learning and informs the public on its policies, norms and opportunities. For Open science in Horizon Europe, read this [infosheet](#).

Training and Education

Even when UBC projects are not solely focused on training and education, they always present mediums for learning and acquiring new knowledge and skills. Partners in UBC consortiums learn from each other. Capacity building through knowledge exchange is appreciated and should be fostered, our research finds. Firstly, HEIs and SMEs would like to learn from others who have undergone different UBC initiatives, implemented large-scale European projects and to share their experiences. Secondly, training and educative activities should be always included in UBC. Opportunity to access new knowledge and improve skills is something that can increase the attractiveness of UBC projects. Such training offers a basis to decrease the mismatch between skills that are needed on the project to be successfully implemented and in general by participating organizations, and of skills

that professionals actually have. A noted barrier is the lack of qualified professionals, especially boundary spanners. Inclusion of students in such training would also widen the skillset in the labour market.

GOOD PRACTICE

Spanning Boundaries Online Training

Through a 5-month programme, this training allows participants to:

- Access to Europe's leading experts and content on UBC
- Engage in peer-learning with national and international participants
- Discover tools and methods to identify and build new partnerships
- Find matchmaking, joint-projects and funding opportunities
- Accelerate their development through their own UBC project

In fact, training of students through UBC projects is highlighted as very beneficial both to HEIs and SMEs as explained earlier in this report. As such, it should be incorporated carefully into collaborative projects. Particularly industrial, innovation and entrepreneurial PhD work should be fostered more, especially in countries where it is still not a common practice, such as Spain and Cyprus. Moreover, through involvement of students in UBC, transdisciplinary and multidisciplinary profiles of future researchers and professionals can be encouraged.

UBC based training allows also for better connection between research and education and valorization since it brings learners directly into programs where these processes are managed coherently. A suggestion was made for HEIs to use businesses partnership models when designing PhD fellowships, where 4-5 thesis assignments can be bundled together which would create a solid foundation for R&D projects and long-term collaborative learning. At the moment, many professors do thesis supervision ad hoc and are unable to pay special attention to the business-development needs of their students. Our research finds that student placements oftentimes does not involve substantial learning. Placements in some instances are not clear on what students should be doing and does not involve development of new skills. Better alignment of university placement programs with the industrial needs should be in place. Through discussions with the business communities, including SMEs, HEIs can determine topics and focus of such placements and develop targeted training. Transdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and entrepreneurial approaches to problem solving should be fostered alongside development of project management skills described in this report. UBC clusters could develop research portfolios as challenges which researchers need to address.

In the recent period, incorporation of online training that can be accessed at any time to diverse audiences has been popular. This trend is on the rise considering the pandemic circumstances. Lots of HEIs and SMEs are interested in these online educative activities, whether as training providers or participants.

Although HEIs have a lot of experts and knowledge in house, only small portion is shared with the public and specific stakeholders. Online courses, MOOCs and similar video enhanced non-formal education has become prominent, especially in the United States. This trend is evident on YouTube, Switch and other social media where distribution of knowledge-based materials is high on demand. HEIs in Europe are lagging behind this trend. Therefore, development of online training and education modules directed towards specific audiences is field of expertise that is needed and looked-for in the UBC community. In this instance, maintenance and potential commercialization of such training products is also something that is of interest, alongside their promotion via online channels, including social media.

5. Opportunities to Support Collaboration

Opportunities for HEIs and SMEs collaborations are diverse. Countries have recognized the innovative role of SMEs and have fostered involvement of small companies in their granting schemes. National agencies that support R&D, innovation and general business development provide funding and matching opportunities. European level support has become more accessible and adjusted to the needs of smaller companies too and more focused on specific targets where such companies can join larger consortiums.

Table 2: The following table provides list of opportunities of some funding schemes and matching tools.

Type	Diverse UBC opportunities for HEIs & SMEs
EU Funding	<p><u>EIC Accelerator</u></p> <p>Through its Accelerator programme, the European Innovation Council supports individual SMEs, in particular Startups and spinout companies to develop and scaleup game-changing innovations. It provides substantial financial support with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) grant funding (non-dilutive) of up to €2.5 million for innovation development costs, ii) investments (direct equity investments) of up to €15 million managed by the EIC Fund for scale up and other relevant costs. <p>In addition, EIC selected companies receive coaching, mentoring, access to investors and corporates, and many other opportunities as part of the EIC community. The EIC welcomes applications from innovators in all EU Member States and countries associated to the Horizon Europe Search for available translations of the preceding Horizon Europe programme. It particularly welcomes applications from startups and SMEs with female CEOs.</p>
	<p><u>Horizon Europe</u></p> <p>As the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation with a budget of €95.5 billion, the Horizon Europe aims to tackle climate change, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth. Particular Pillar II offers lots of opportunities for SME participation.</p>
	<p><u>Erasmus+ Alliances for innovation Programme</u></p> <p>This program aims to strengthen Europe's innovation capacity by boosting innovation through cooperation and flow of knowledge among higher education, vocational education and training (both initial and continuous), and the broader socio-economic environment, including research.</p>
	<p>They also aim to boost the provision of new skills and address skills mismatches by designing and creating new curricula for higher education (HE) and vocational education and training (VET), supporting the development of a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial mind-sets in the EU.</p>

<p>Matching</p>	<p><u>The CrowdHelix Network</u></p> <p>This network connects a group of leading research institutions & innovating companies around the world, so that together they can plan & deliver pioneering Horizon Europe projects. It is open to any organisation, of any size, anywhere in the world, that can demonstrate a strategic commitment to collaborative research and innovation. This platform allows academics to have direct contact with SMEs, but it also allows those supporting partnership engagement to facilitate the contact on behalf of the academics.</p> <p><u>International Association of Science Parks and Areas of Innovation</u></p> <p>This global network of science parks and areas of innovation aims to drive growth, internationalisation and effectiveness for its 350 current members.</p> <p><u>Collabwith</u> is a platform that allows researchers and SMEs to connect. This platform is not only around Horizon Europe, but for SMEs looking for consultancy services too.</p>
<p>Learning</p>	<p><u>University-Industry Innovation Network (UIIN)</u></p> <p>Through an Annual conference and a range of workshops around UBC , UIIN brings together extensive number of HEI and business representatives together for learning and matching sessions.</p> <p><u>ASTP Trainings and Tools</u></p> <p>ASTP is Europe's non-profit association of knowledge transfer professionals. Through their website they offer professional accreditation, professional development and other services to their members.</p> <p><u>HEInnovate Workshops</u></p> <p>The European Commission and OECD support HEIs through these workshops to assess their current situation and identify potential areas for action for entrepreneurial and innovative HEIs.</p> <p><u>Online Thematic Workshop on the University-Industry Collaboration</u></p> <p>The Interreg Europe through its Policy Learning Platform offered this 3-hour workshop in March 2021 which included panel discussion, practice presentation, and group work for pitch presentation by universities (public laboratories, research institutes etc.) and industry (private companies). The workshop is recorded and available online.</p> <p><u>ECIU University Challenges</u></p> <p>The European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU) provides this program in forms of a challenge designed for students from 12 ECIU member universities that are located in 12 different European countries. It aims to offer training to students and guides them to engage with business companies or societal partners so as to solve a real-life challenge together.</p> <p><u>Strengthening University-Industry Partnerships</u></p>

This program implemented by the University-Industry Demonstration Partnership (UIDP), a US-based organization takes place each year on a semi-regular basis and covers wide range of UBC topics and issues.

Strategic Partnerships Online Program

Provided by the Institute for Management Development (IMD), this eight-week digital program begins with a deep dive into the fundamental building blocks of leveraging successful strategic partnerships for competitive advantage and continues later on with application of frameworks for a specific strategic partnership challenge.

6. Methodology

This Synthesis report summarizes the all Unite4Horizon research findings and offers overview of competencies and fields of knowledge that were pinpointed as crucial for university-business collaboration and especially for cooperation between researchers/academics and SME representatives. To provide useful analytical insights this report explores the university and SME readiness to engage in collaboration from both i) the theory (literature reviews), and ii) the practice (interviews, case studies, and the survey). In particular, this report seeks to:

- a) identify the status-quo: of academics and SME representatives' engagement skills and competences, and determine the facilitators, challenges, as well as perceived partnership opportunities,
- b) identify the previous experience (with Horizon 2020), interest and engagement potential of academics and SME representatives for Horizon Europe and other European funding programmes,
- c) identify strategies/approaches to foster HEI-SME engagement in each region.

The research behind this report entailed mixed-methods and extensive data collection in European and national level contexts. Each partner organization in the Project Consortium conducted research in their respective country using their existing networks and knowledge-based while building onto new contacts and insights. These findings were used to identify patterns that span national context and mapped issues. In particular, the research incorporated the following:

- Desk research on HEIs-SMEs engagement in European and national context in Cyprus, Finland, France, Ireland, Germany, and Spain;
- Benchmarking analysis of existing UBC training programmes;
- Expert interviews with 49 academics and engagement officers, SME representatives, European funding programme experts, and non-university engagement professionals;
- Survey with 217 participants among target groups from 24 countries in Europe;
- Case studies of 35 successful HEI-SME partnerships identified among the funded Horizon 2020 projects.

Each research method was designed to map particular practices and aspects of UBC collaboration from the HEIs-SMEs engagement perspective.

6.1.1. Desk Research

An extensive desktop review of relevant scientific and grey literature in the fields of university-business cooperation and university and SME engagement was undertaken in order to provide a **background**

and foundation for understanding the national status-quo of academics and SME representatives' engagement skills and competences, as well as facilitators, challenges, and perceived partnership opportunities **with a specific focus on Horizon Europe and European funding programmes in general.**

Specifically, in relation to the **HEI-SME engagement** the following was mapped:

- The context of **university-business engagement in the given countries** including the engagement facilitators, challenges, perceived partnership opportunities and benefits.
- The **national contexts** in terms of existing and potential **support mechanisms** (policy, strategic, structural or operational) available for universities and SMEs to collaborate as part of Horizon Europe and further European funding programs.
- The current state of **university 'engagement capacity'** with a focus on collaborative innovation including:
 - motivations for collaboration,
 - challenges associated with collaboration,
 - skills and competencies required,
 - supporting mechanisms and resources needs, and
 - potential opportunities for university-industry engagement in the national contexts as part of Horizon Europe and further European funding programs.
- The current state of **SME 'engagement capacity'** with a focus on collaborative innovation:
 - motivations for collaboration,
 - challenges associated with collaboration,
 - skills and competencies required,
 - supporting mechanisms and resources needs, and
 - potential opportunities for university-industry engagement in the national contexts as part of Horizon Europe and further European funding programs.

6.1.2. Benchmarking Analysis

Our benchmarking analysis incorporated a straightforward process of mapping existing training programs designed to foster UBC collaboration. The aim was to identify what already exists on the market, who has access, what the focus on the training program is, etc. In particular, the following categories for 8 training programs were used:

- Program Name
- Organisation
- Time
- Duration
- Format
- Target Group
- Focus
- Summary
- Website link

6.1.3. Expert Interviews

Semi-structured interviews with 49 academics and engagement officers, SME representatives, European funding programme experts, and non-university engagement professionals were designed to explore:

- The current state of **university ‘engagement capacity’** with a focus on collaborative innovation including:
 - motivations for collaboration,
 - challenges or barriers associated with collaboration,
 - supporting mechanisms and resource needs for collaboration,
 - skills and capabilities (self-assessment) underpinning collaboration
- Specifically relating to the **Horizon2020 program**:
 - Experience - the previous experiences with cooperation as part of European funding programs (e.g. Horizon 2020),
 - Capabilities – the specific skills and support required for HEI-SME engagement as part of European funding programmes
 - Opportunities – the specific opportunities that might exist for HEI-SME engagement in terms of topics (horizontal or vertical) in research, education and valorisation (commercialisation and entrepreneurship) with regards to European funding programmes
 - Strategies – the successful strategies/approaches to foster HEI-SME engagement for collaboration as part of European funding programme.

6.1.4. Survey

The survey data used in this report explored the following:

1. **Status quo:** The extent to which Horizon2020 (historically) and Horizon Europe have been (through participation) or are currently interesting to respondents (interest in participating);
2. That specifically explores the **Horizon2020 program:**
 - Experience - the previous experiences with cooperation as part of European funding programs (e.g. Horizon 2020),
 - Capabilities – the specific skills and support required for HEI-SME engagement as part of European funding programmes
 - Opportunities – the specific opportunities that might exist for HEI-SME engagement in terms of topics (horizontal or vertical) in research, education and valorisation (commercialisation and entrepreneurship) with regards to European funding programmes
 - Strategies – the successful strategies/approaches to foster HEI-SME engagement for collaboration as part of European funding programmes,
3. To collect representative data:
 - through consolidating **217 survey responses** (academics and SME representatives across Europe)
 - to provide supplementary analysis and cross verification for the previous interview report.

A full report of the survey results are available in a separate document.

6.1.5. Case Studies

Ultimately, 35 case study reports were prepared based on combination of desk research and interviews which:

1. Provide succinct descriptions on the practice of successful HEI-SME partnerships, from various perspectives including industry, SME characteristics, engagement methods, etc. both:
 - General HEI-SME partnerships cases
 - From the Horizon2020 program
2. Summarise key factors leading to such successful partnership that can be learned or enhanced by other SMEs including the description of:
 - motivations for collaboration,
 - challenges or barriers associated with collaboration,
 - supporting mechanisms and resource needs for collaboration,
 - skills and capabilities (self-assessment) underpinning collaboration.
3. Provide implications and suggestions for HEIs and SMEs to establish successful partnerships or to enhance their existing partnerships.

7. Annex: List of expert interviews and case studies

Country	Expert interviews	Case studies
European level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christina Achilleos, Head of Innovation & Erasmus+ Units, GrantXpert Consulting Ltd Kimberly CornField, Head of European Research and Innovation, University College London Nikolaos Floratos, Research and Innovation coach, Funding Expert Academy Dipti Pandya, Senior Manager, Research Programmes, University College Dublin Gabriella Lovasz, Managing Director, Europa Media Neeltje Ramnath, Head of Agri, Food and Bioeconomy, Catalyze Troels Jacobsen, Director of Innovation and societal engagement, University of Stavanger 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biomass Technology Group Geonardo Martel UNIFE WiMUST
Cyprus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anastasia Petrou, Officer, ILO UNIC Office Nearchos Paspallis, Assistant Professor in Computing, University of Central Lancashire Cyprus (UCLan) Panayiotis Zaphiris, Rector & Professor, Cyprus University of Technology Tasos Kounoudes, CEO, SignalGeneriX Ltd Panayiotis Philimis, CEO, CYRIC Costas Sisamos, CEO, Engino.net Ltd 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phoebe Research and Innovation CyRic Cyprus University of Technology & GeofEM LTD Partnership European University Cyprus University of Technology partnership with a winery
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Harri Ketamo, Founder & Chairman, HeadAI Tomi Pajala, Entrepreneur, Fimentum Oy Pirita Ihamäki, Leader of Gamecoast Network, Prizztech/Gamecoast Pasi Teräväinen, Specialist, JAMK University of Applied Sciences Isto Mattila, RDI Director, Laurea University of Applied Sciences Jatta Jussila, CEO, Clic Innovations Oy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIMECC Ltd Finest love from Crazy Town Oy Robocoast (Prizztech) Metropolia University of Applied Sciences 3AMK Alliance of three universities of applied sciences (Haaga-Helia, Laurea, & Metropolia)
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Philippe Cousin, Founder, Easy Global Market SAS Marie Carpenter, Strategy Lecturer, IMTBS Julien Hering, CEO, Tree of Sciences SAS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IMT Mines d'Alès hive.mobility, University of Groningen

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iris Kerambrun, European Project Manager, Sorbonne Université • Gaëtan Lan Sun Luk, Director of Innovation & Partnerships, Université de Montpellier • Emma France, Impact Entrepreneurship Program Manager, HEC Paris 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Mobility Research Lab, University of Bologna • Institut Mines-Télécom
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Falk Ritschel, CEO, Conomic GmbH • Karsten Schwarz, Practical Researcher, Medical Faculty Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg • Monika Lelonek, Project Manager, SmartMembranes GmbH • Heike Gebhardt, Project Manager, MITZ Merseburger Innovations- und Technologiezentrum GmbH • Martin Wagner, CEO, Micro Pro GmbH • Andreas Fiedler, Project Manager, brain-SCC GmbH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adsata • Mimi Hearing Technologies • GmbH BioSolutions Halle GmbH (BSH)
Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Siobhan Keogh, Manager, Regional Skills Forum • Neil McLoughlin, Technology Transfer Manager, Dundalk Technical University • Lorna Cooney, Senior Enterprise Development Officer, Local Enterprise Office • Gary O'Meara, Chief Executive, NACEC National Association of Enterprise Centres • Conor Patterson, Chief eExecutive, WIN Consultants • Aidan Browne, Director, Regional Development Centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Little Sunflower • Village Vets • Ireland Planner • GH Best • Ardee Sports
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maria Vazquez, Software Engineer, Vázquez y Torres Ingeniería SL (VTI) • Laura Iglesias, Head of the Innovation Area of the General Directorate of Research and Technological Innovation of the Community of Madrid • Daniel Jaque, Doctor of Physical Sciences, Autonomous University of Madrid • Jesus Perez Gil, Professor in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology and Dean of the Faculty of Biology, Complutense University of Madrid • Luis Sanz, Managing Director, IASP (International Association of Science Parks and Areas of Innovation) • Jose Maria Labeaga, Professor of Fundamentals of Economic Analysis, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AEQ • B5TEC • Sensia Solutions SL • QI4 Consulting • NIMGENTICS

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Irene Martin, Contracted Professor Doctor, Autonomous University of Madrid• Jean Baptiste, Business Developer, Heroux-Devtek• Rodrigo Garcia, Chief Operation Officer (COO), Gas and Go Global Services• Juan Ignacio Martinez, Director of Communication, Dantia• Antonio Zerolo, Director, Anzeve• Juan Jose Vaquero, Professor of Bioengineering / Vice-Rector for Scientific Policy, University Carlos III of Madrid	
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